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Demonstration of a SAR Interferometry Training Dataset for Forest Parameter Retrieval

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Abstract

Estimating forest height is crucial for monitoring forest health, carbon storage, timber resources, biodiversity, and ecosystem dynamics. While Interferometric SAR has shown great potential in this domain, machine learning algorithms are increasingly favored for their scalability and efficiency in handling large datasets. Deep learning, particularly with Sentinel-1's global Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) coverage, offers a powerful approach for automating forest parameter estimation. However, the success of AI-driven methods relies on access to high-quality benchmark datasets with comprehensive annotations.

To address this need, an ESA-funded project is developing a benchmark dataset that integrates pre-processed Sentinel-1 polarimetric interferometric data with forest height annotations derived from space-based LiDAR. This dataset spans diverse forest types worldwide, incorporates varying temporal baselines, and includes geocoded polarimetric-interferometric covariance matrices. Together, these elements provide a robust foundation for advancing machine learning models in forest monitoring.

In this work, we demonstrate the new benchmark dataset by applying state-of-the-art forest height retrieval algorithms, offering a reference for future research and development.

Preface

I would like to thank Prof. Jaan Praks for his guidance throughout this project, and Hossein and Erkki for their help at key moments.

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Barcelona, 22 June 2025

Pablo Jiménez Gascón. Engineer

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Symbols and abbreviations

Symbols

S	Scattering matrix
S_{pq}	Complex amplitude of the scattered signal in polarization p , when transmitted in polarization q
$ S_{pq} $	Absolute value of the scattered signal
$e^{j\phi_{pq}}$	Phase of the scattered signal
k	Pauli vector
T	Coherency matrix
C	Covariance matrix
s	Lexicographic vector $[S_{HH}, S_{HV}, S_{VV}]^T$
λ	Wavelength
R	Distance between the radar and the target
L	Effective length of the synthetic aperture
$A(x, y)$	Amplitude of the radar echo, $—S(x,y)—$
$\phi(x, y)$	Interferometric phase of the echo, $\arg(S(x,y))$
a_n	Amplitude of each point scatterer within the resolution cell
ϕ_n	Phase of each point scatterer within the resolution cell
$I_{pq}(x, y)$	Intensity
ϕ_1	Expected phase of signal 1
ϕ_2	Expected phase of signal 2
ΔR	Path difference
$\Delta\phi$	Interferometric phase difference
B	Baseline
B_{\perp}	Perpendicular baseline
α_{IF}	Interferometric sensitivity factor
HoA	Height of ambiguity
θ	Radar incidence angle
α	Orientation angle of the baseline
γ	Interferometric coherence
$\gamma_{baseline}$	System-related factors decorrelation
γ_{SNR}	Signal to noise decorrelation
γ_{temp}	Temporal decorrelation
γ_{vol}	Volume decorrelation
$\gamma(\vec{k}_z, \vec{p})$	Polarimetric interferometric coherence
\vec{p}	Specific polarization direction
\vec{k}_z	Vertical wave vector
\vec{w}	Complex polarization vector
μ_v	Relative weight of the volume
μ_g	Relative weight of the ground
γ_v	Coherence of the volume
γ_g	Coherence of the ground
h	Forest height

$P(z)$	Vertical distribution of scatterer density
σ	Volume extinction coefficient
M	Ratio between the energy reflected by the ground and the energy scattered by the volume
σ_{disp}	Variance
δ_{motion}	Coherence loss due to the motion
γ_{RVoG}	Coherence of the RVoG model
γ_{RMoG}	Coherence of the RMoG model
σ_v	Volume specific temporal decorrelation
σ_g	Ground specific temporal decorrelation
r	Pearson correlation coefficient
x_i	Individual values of the x set
y_i	Individual values of the y set
\bar{x}	Mean of the x set
\bar{y}	Mean of the y set
$Cov(X, Y)$	Covariance between variables X and Y
n	Number of elements in a set

Operators

$\langle \cdot \rangle$	Spatial average or Multilook
S^H	Hermitian transpose of matrix S
$ s $	Absolute value of the signal s
$arg(s)$	Phase of the signal s
$\sum_{n=1}^N$	Summation from 1 to N
s^*	Complex conjugate of the signal s

Abbreviations

<i>SAR</i>	Synthetic Aperture Radar
<i>InSAR</i>	Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry
<i>PolSAR</i>	Synthetic Aperture Radar Polarimetry
<i>PolInSAR</i>	Polarimetric Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry
<i>BSA</i>	Backscatter Alignment convention
<i>H</i>	Horizontal polarization
<i>V</i>	Vertical polarization
<i>GBSAR</i>	Ground Based Synthetic Aperture Radar
<i>DEM</i>	Digital Elevation Model
<i>CHM</i>	Canopy Height Model
<i>DTM</i>	Digital Terrain Model
<i>HoA</i>	Height of Ambiguity
<i>SNR</i>	Signal to Noise Ratio
<i>RVoG</i>	Random Volume over Ground
<i>RMoG</i>	Random Motion over Ground
<i>LiDAR</i>	Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging
<i>ESA</i>	European Spatial Agency
<i>DLR</i>	German Aerospace Center
<i>ALS</i>	Airborne Laser Scanning
<i>IW</i>	Interferometric Wide Swath
<i>SLC</i>	Single Look Complex
<i>RMSE</i>	Root Mean Square Error
<i>mAmp</i>	Model amplitude scaling factor for coherence
<i>ext</i>	Volume extinction coefficient in RVoG
<i>ph</i>	Phase offset or ground phase in model fitting
<i>PCA</i>	Principal Component Analysis

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1 Introduction

Monitoring forest structure and its evolution is essential for understanding carbon cycles, managing natural resources and evaluating ecosystem health in the context of global change. Remote sensing technologies, especially radar-based methods, offer robust tools for assessing forest parameters at large scale, independently of cloud cover and illumination conditions.

Among these technologies, Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry (InSAR) has emerged as a powerful technique for retrieving topographic and structural information by exploiting phase differences between multiple radar acquisitions. When combined with polarimetric diversity, as in Polarimetric SAR Interferometry (PolInSAR), the resulting framework enables the separation of scattering mechanisms and the estimation of vertical forest structure, particularly canopy heights and biomass.

This thesis focuses on the physical modeling and empirical analysis of InSAR and PolInSAR coherence in forested areas, with special emphasis on the relationship between interferometric observables and forest structural parameters. The study explores the applicability of two key physical models, Random Volume over Ground (RVoG), which models volume and ground contributions in coherent radar observations, and Random Movement over Ground (RMoG), as an extension that incorporates the effects of temporal decorrelation, allowing for improved representation of coherence in repeat-pass SAR acquisitions.

The methodology is applied to a set of diverse datasets, including Airborne and LiDAR-calibrated single baseline acquisitions over boreal forest in Estonia and Finland, enabling direct model validation, and Sentinel-1 repeat-pass time series, affected by temporal decorrelation, used to assess the robustness and limitations of coherence based inversion under real satellite conditions.

The general objective of this thesis is to evaluate the capacity of physically based InSAR and PolInSAR models to retrieve forest structural parameters, particularly canopy height, across different SAR acquisition configurations. Specifically, the study aims to:

- (1) Calibrate and validate the RVoG and RMoG models using airborne L-band PolInSAR data from Estonian and Finnish forests with LiDAR reference.
- (2) Assess the applicability of these models to satellite-based observations affected by temporal decorrelation, such as Sentinel-1 C-band time-series.
- (3) Explore the behavior of interferometric coherence across seasons, polarizations, incidence angles, and vertical wavenumbers to identify patterns that could support both model-based and data-driven monitoring approaches.

To achieve the objectives explained, this thesis is structured as follows, chapter 2 provides the theoretical framework, including the fundamentals of radar scattering, SAR imaging, interferometric coherence and polarimetric analysis, chapter 3 describes the physical models used for forest parameter inversion, including their mathematical formulation and adaptation to the available data. Chapter 4 presents the experimental results, exploring the coherence-height relationship and temporal analysis across different forest regions and

acquisition geometries, and chapter 5 summarized the main findings and outlines potential future research directions.

By combining physically based modeling with multi-source remote sensing data, this work contributes to the development of more interpretable and scalable methods for forest structure estimation using SAR technologies.

The main objective of this thesis is to evaluate the capacity of physically based InSAR and PolInSAR models to retrieve forest structural parameters, particularly canopy height, across diverse acquisition configurations. To this end, the study aims to calibrate and validate the RVoG and RMoG models over airborne datasets with LiDAR reference data and to assess their applicability to satellite based observations subject to temporal decorrelation, such as Sentinel-1. In parallel, the work explores the behavior of interferometric coherence across seasons, polarizations, incidence angles and vertical wavenumbers in order to identify patterns that may support model driven or data driven forest monitoring strategies.

1.1 Chronogram

To provide a clear overview of the project’s development, the following Gantt chart outlines the main phases and milestones of the thesis work. The timeline spans from the initial literature review and theoretical consolidation to the implementation of the models, data analysis and final documentation. This structured schedule reflects the iterative nature of research and the progressive integration of theoretical understanding with experimental results.

Figure 1: Gantt chart of the thesis development timeline.

2 SAR Interferometry and Coherent Remote Sensing

2.1 Radar Measurement Principles

Radar remote sensing is based on the transmission and reception of electromagnetic waves. A radar system emits a known waveform and records the backscattered response from the scene. These responses are modeled as complex valued signals, where both amplitude and phase carry physical information [9, 8].

An electromagnetic wave propagating along the z axis can be described by a transverse electric field,

$$E(z, t) = \begin{bmatrix} E_x(z, t) \\ E_y(z, t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_x \cdot e^{j(kR - wt + \phi_x)} \\ A_y \cdot e^{j(kR - wt + \phi_y)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

Where A_x and A_y are the amplitudes of the horizontal and vertical components and ϕ_x and ϕ_y are their respective phases. k is the wavenumber equal to $\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ and w is the angular frequency. The vector $E(z, t)$ defines not only the intensity of the wave but also its polarization, i.e., the shape and orientation of the electric field in the transverse plane. Polarization plays a central role in how radar waves interact with targets as vegetation, water or structures [33].

The radar measures the electric field and the effect that the target has on the polarization of the wave is calculated by processing the ratio between the transmitted and received signal. This is described by the complex scattering matrix S , which relates the transmitted and received polarized components [8, 33],

$$[E_{pq}^{rec}] = [S] \cdot [E_{pq}^{tx}], \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_H^{rec} \\ E_V^{rec} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{HH} & S_{HV} \\ S_{VH} & S_{VV} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} E_H^{tx} \\ E_V^{tx} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Each term S_{pq} represents a complex scattering coefficient, where p and q denote the transmit and receive polarization channels, H or V. These coefficients are the fundamental radar observables and inform how the target reflects energy between polarization states [9]. The values of S_{pq} depend on the physical properties and geometry of the scatterer.

Figure 2: Polarization channels.

In a Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) system, the radar coherently processes these scattered signals across multiple spatial positions to form high-resolution images. Each pixel in a SAR image contains a complex number derived from one of the S_{pq} components, representing both amplitude and phase. This phase encodes the two way travel distance between the radar and the scatterer [10],

$$S_{pq} \approx A_{pq} \cdot e^{-j \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda}}, \quad (4)$$

where R is the distance from radar to target and λ the wavelength. Due to the fact that this measurement is coherent, the radar can compare acquisitions from different times or slightly different positions giving rise to the concept of interferometric coherence [42].

Given two complex radar acquisitions $S_{pq}^{(1)}$ and $S_{pq}^{(2)}$, the complex coherence is defined as,

$$\gamma = \frac{\langle S_{pq}^{(1)} \cdot S_{pq}^{(2)*} \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle |S_{pq}^{(1)}|^2 \rangle \cdot \langle |S_{pq}^{(2)}|^2 \rangle}}. \quad (5)$$

This coherence is a unitless complex quantity whose magnitude $|\gamma| \in [0, 1]$ indicates the level of similarity between both acquisitions. $|\gamma| \approx 1$ represents high similarity so a stable scene, $|\gamma| \ll 1$ means that the scene has changed or significant decorrelation occurred. The phase of γ relates differences in path length between acquisitions and is exploited in interferometric SAR (InSAR) and polarimetric interferometry (PolInSAR) for retrieving height, deformation or structure [33, 20].

In forested or volumetric areas, the radar return is originated from many scatterers distributed in height. These contributions are not stationary and may change due to wind, growth or sensor noise. As a result, the total coherence can be modeled as the product of multiple factors [25, 24],

$$\gamma = \gamma_{SNR} \cdot \gamma_{baseline} \cdot \gamma_{vol} \cdot \gamma_{temp} \quad (6)$$

These coherence components are essential in the modeling and inversion strategies presented in the following chapters, particularly in retrieving forest structure from PolInSAR data.

2.2 Principles of SAR Imaging

Following the electromagnetic and polarization foundations presented in Section 2.1, we now focus on the image formation mechanism employed by SAR systems. SAR exploits the coherent nature of radar signals to synthetically enlarge the antenna aperture and achieve fine azimuth resolution through signal processing.

SAR systems operate in side looking geometries and transmit sequences of modulated pulses while moving along a linear trajectory as shown in Figure 3. As the platform advances, each ground resolution cell is illuminated multiple times under slightly different observation angles. These echoes are coherently recorded and then combined via matched filtering algorithms to form a focused, complex valued image [10, 13].

Figure 3: Typical SAR imaging geometry.

The spatial resolution in SAR images is controlled by two independent parameters, Range resolution, governed by the bandwidth of the transmitted pulse and Azimuth resolution, determined by the synthetic aperture length, which depends on the coherent integration of Doppler-shifted returns along the flight path.

By simulating a large aperture through motion, SAR systems can achieve meter or sub-meter level resolution from airborne or spaceborne platforms, without requiring physically large antennas [8, 12].

SAR instruments operate across a wide range of microwave frequencies, from P-band to Ka-band, each suited to specific applications [10]. Table 1 summarizes the main radar frequency bands and their typical characteristics.

Table 1: SAR main frequency bands.

Band	Frequency Ranges (GHz)	Wavelengths (cm)	Applications
P	0.3 - 1.0	30 - 100	Penetration into Soils and Dense Vegetation
L	1.0 - 2.0	15 - 30	Studies on Forests, Geodesy, or Glaciers
S	2.0 - 4.0	7.5 - 15	Meteorological and Environmental Applications
C	4.0 - 8.0	3.75 - 7.5	Monitoring of Oceans, Agriculture, and Land Deformations
X	8.0 - 12.0	2.5 - 3.75	High-Resolution Mapping or Urban Studies
Ku/K/Ka	12.0 - 40.0	0.75 - 2.5	Applications in Meteorological Radars and Satellite Altimetry

The choice of frequency band directly impacts the penetration depth, sensitivity to surface structure and achievable spatial resolution. Longer wavelengths, L-,P-bands, offer increased penetration into vegetation and soil, which is essential for forest height and biomass retrieval applications [9].

Depending on the required resolution and coverage, SAR sensors can be deployed on satellites, aircraft or ground based (GB) systems. Satellite missions such as Sentinel-1 and ALOS-2 enable large scale systematic monitoring, while airborne and GB-SAR platforms offer greater temporal flexibility and higher resolution for regional studies [19, 29, 7].

2.2.1 Complex SAR Signal and Its Interpretation

The fundamental output of a SAR system is a complex valued image, in which each pixel represents the coherent integration of backscattered signals from a finite ground resolution cell. Unlike optical sensors, SAR does not form a direct image of isolated targets, but rather captures the collective electromagnetic response of a distributed set of scatters within each resolution cell [33, 8].

From a signal processing perspective, the received signal in a SAR pixel is the result of the convolution between the system's point spread function and the scene reflectivity. In the absence of strong isolated targets, the signal can be modeled as a complex sum of N elemental scatters [33],

$$s = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n \cdot e^{j\phi_n} \quad (7)$$

where a_n and ϕ_n are the amplitude and phase contributions of the $n - th$ scatterer. These contributions are modulated by factors such as the local incidence angle, dielectric properties or sub-pixel geometry [42].

This summation leads to constructive and destructive interference, resulting in the phenomenon known as speckle. This is an intrinsic feature of coherent imaging systems and encodes the statistical behavior of the scene. Although it appears as noise in intensity images, speckle contains phase information crucial for important interferometric and polarimetric applications [9]. Each complex pixel encodes both, amplitude, related to the total backscattered power from the resolution cell and phase, determined by the relative propagation path and the geometry of the scattering elements.

When multiple SAR acquisitions are available over the same region, the coherent nature of the signal enables advanced processing techniques as InSAR, based on phase differences between acquisitions, PolSAR, based on scattering diversity across polarizations or PolInSAR, which jointly exploits both dimensions [33, 42].

In polarimetric systems, different polarization channels, HH, HV, VH and VV, are recorded simultaneously, resulting in a set of complex valued images. This can be grouped into a scattering matrix and further vectorized for statistical modeling as detailed in Section 2.3.

This interpretation of SAR images as coherent, complex valued data provides the analytical foundation for all subsequent modeling and inversion techniques presented along this thesis.

2.3 SAR Interferometry

Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometry is an advanced remote sensing technique that enables millimeter-scale measurements of Earth's surface topography and displacements [3, 8, 10]. This method relies on comparing the phase of radar waves reflected from the ground in two SAR images acquired from slightly different positions in space or at different times [2, 3].

Each SAR image contains complex information in every pixel, represented by the scattering matrix (3) introduced earlier. For a given ground location, InSAR compares two measurements S_1 and S_2 , typically corresponding to the same polarization channel S_{pq} , acquired at different times or from slightly different positions. The resulting interferometric phase is sensitive to the relative path length and thus encodes information about the terrain height or dynamic surface changes.

InSAR has a wide range of applications in various scientific and industrial fields. In cartography and terrain modeling, it is used to generate high-resolution Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) that offer accurate representations of the Earth's surface [3, 19]. For monitoring land deformation, it is a fundamental tool for measuring tectonic movements, urban subsidence, or ground subsidence caused by human activities such as groundwater extraction or mining [6, 7]. In the surveillance of natural phenomena such as volcanic eruptions and earthquakes, it detects changes in the Earth's surface before and after seismic events or eruption, contributing to natural disaster prevention and management [1, 4].

Figure 4: Interferometric SAR radar beams.

In the study of glaciers and ice dynamics, InSAR facilitates the measurement of displacements and structural variations in glaciers, providing crucial information in the context of climate change [7]. For infrastructure monitoring, it helps evaluate the structural stability of building, bridges, dams, or slopes over time [2].

In the present work, the focus is on InSAR and its polarimetric interferometry variant, introduced below, for forest remote sensing, specifically in canopy height estimation and biomass characterization [17, 25]. Such applications are of great importance for the sustainable management of forest resources and for assessing the environmental impact on ecosystems.

The main configurations for acquiring InSAR data are as follows:

1. Repeat-pass InSAR: A single satellite acquires images at different times, making it susceptible to temporal decorrelation. It is used to detect accumulated ground deformations over extended periods [32].
2. Single-pass InSAR: Two antennas installed on the same platform acquire images simultaneously, thereby eliminating temporal decorrelation. It is primarily employed to generate high-precision DEMs [19].
3. Bistatic InSAR: Two independent satellites acquire images in a coordinated manner. It is used in applications requiring high interferometric accuracy [4].

The physical and geometric foundations of interferometric phase generation are developed in the next subsection.

2.3.1 Principle of SAR Interferometric Measurement

The fundamental principle of InSAR, as mentioned earlier, is based on measuring the phase difference between two SAR images acquired from two slightly different positions in space or at different times. This phase difference is used to extract information about the terrain's topology of surface displacements by estimating changes in the signal's propagation distance [3, 8, 10].

To better understand this principle, one can consider a SAR system with two antennas or two distinct positions of the same satellite, both of which transmit and receive radar signals. As illustrated in Figure 5, the same ground target is observed from both perspectives resulting in a path length difference ΔR . This difference causes a phase shift proportional to itself and the radar wavelength.

Figure 5: SAR Interferometry.

Assuming a side looking radar configuration and a perpendicular baseline B_{\perp} , the interferometric phase difference can be approximated by [21],

$$\Delta\phi = \phi_1 - \phi_2 = 4\pi \frac{\Delta R}{\lambda}. \quad (8)$$

The quantity ΔR itself depends on the acquisition geometry and is influenced by the incidence angle θ and the baseline orientation α . For spaceborne SAR configurations, where $B \ll R$, as in this thesis, we can use [21] the law of cosines,

$$(R + \Delta R)^2 = R^2 + B^2 - 2RB \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta + \alpha\right). \quad (9)$$

Then, the expression of ΔR can be simplified as [21],

$$\Delta R \approx -B \sin(\theta - \alpha), \quad (10)$$

leading to the widely used relation [21],

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{-2\pi}{\lambda} B \sin(\theta - \alpha). \quad (11)$$

This formulation reveals the phase sensitivity to variations in topography and acquisition geometry. In practice, B_{\perp} plays a key role, longer baselines increase sensitivity to vertical structure, but also to noise and decorrelation effects. Note that interferometric phase arises from (5), as the phase of interferometric coherence, discussed in the next chapter.

From this, the concept of height of ambiguity (HoA) is derived [21], defined as the height difference corresponding to a full 2π phase cycle,

$$HoA = \frac{\lambda R \sin(\theta)}{B_{\perp}} = \frac{1}{kz}. \quad (12)$$

This parameter normalizes elevation measurements across different baselines and allows coherent comparison across interferometric datasets.

As discussed in Appendix 5.1, these geometric relationships are the foundation of InSAR-based Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and displacements mapping. For example, deviations from a reference phase in flat terrain reflect either topographic relief or surface motion between acquisitions. Consequently, precise knowledge of geometry and baseline orientation is essential for interpreting phase information and for all further model development presented in this thesis.

2.3.2 Interferometric Coherence

Interferometric coherence is a fundamental measure in InSAR systems, as explained in Section 2.1, it quantifies the degree of correlation between two complex SAR signals received from slightly different positions or times. Mathematically, it is defined as the normalized complex cross-correlation between two signals, as defined in (5). Where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denote a spatial average, typically over a window of several pixels to reduce noise. The magnitude of the coherence $|\gamma|$ provides a normalized measure of phase consistency ranging from 0, indicating complete decorrelation, to 1, representing perfect coherence, ideal for interferometric applications[2, 3, 32].

In general, the measured coherence can be modeled as the product of several independent factors, as presented in (6). Each representing a different source of coherence loss in which $\gamma_{baseline}$ accounts for decorrelation caused by system-related factors such as baseline errors [1, 4]. γ_{SNR} refers to coherence loss induced by a low signal-to-noise ratio. γ_{temp} represents temporal decorrelation, i.e., changes in the target between the two acquisitions [24]. Finally, γ_{vol} refers to volume decorrelation, from distributed scatterers within the vertical structure, it could be seen as the target decorrelation or forest decorrelation [17, 25].

Among these, temporal and volume decorrelation dominate in vegetated areas. Volume decorrelation arises from the random distribution of scattering elements along the vertical axis, typical in forest canopies, leading to partial loss of coherence even under stable observation conditions. In contrast, temporal decorrelation reflects real changes in the scene between acquisitions.

In this thesis, coherence is used as a structural indicator of forest canopies. Under the assumption of negligible temporal decorrelation, as in single-pass or short temporal baselines, the measured γ can be interpreted primarily as a function of γ_{vol} , thus enabling biophysical parameter retrieval such as canopy height [25, 24].

However, as pointed out in [24], the distinction between γ_{vol} and γ_{temp} is not always straightforward. Understanding and accurately modeling these decorrelation sources is essential for applying physically based inversion models such as the RVoG and RMoG, which are developed in the next chapter, also it is possible to identify other coherence contributions, such as surface scattering of any other specific contribution.

2.4 Polarimetric SAR Interferometry

Polarimetric SAR Interferometry is an advanced technique that combines the geometric sensitivity of InSAR with the structural characterization capabilities of PolSAR, enabling the extraction of three-dimensional information about the observed medium from the coherence between SAR images acquired from different positions and polarizations [25, 26].

This technique is particularly useful in volumetric media, such as forest or snow, where the radar return originates from multiple depths. In such scenarios, the interferometric radar signal varies not only with geometry but also with the vertical structure of the medium. Its main application lies in the estimations of biophysical forest parameters, such as canopy height, as it enables the separation of the signal reflected from the tree canopy from that of the ground. Moreover, it allows the distinction between different scattering mechanisms, significantly improving the system's accuracy [28, 29, 31].

Figure 6: SAR polarimetric measurement modes.

2.4.1 Scattering Matrix

In PolSAR systems, the radar transmits and receives electromagnetic waves in orthogonal polarization states, typically horizontal (H) and vertical (V), and records the complex backscattered signals associated with each polarization combination [8, 9].

These complex values are not independent of one another but are coherently grouped into the so-called scattering matrix S , introduced in Section 2.1 which characterizes the transformation of the incident field by the target medium [33, 27].

For mono-static systems, under the *Backscatter Alignment* (BSA) convention, the scattering matrix is expressed as (3).

Under ideal conditions of electromagnetic symmetry, such as in linear, homogeneous and isotropic media, the principle of electromagnetic reciprocity holds,

$$S_{HV} = S_{VH}, \quad (13)$$

reducing the independent elements to 3 [8, 33]. This compact representation is the foundation of polarimetric processing, allowing for the identification of canonical scattering mechanisms, *Surface Scattering*, $|S_{HH}| \gg |S_{HV}|$, typical of smooth surfaces such as water bodies or bare soils, *Double-Bounce Scattering*, $|S_{HV}| \approx |S_{HH}|$, commonly observed in vertical structures such as trees or man-made objects, and *Volume Scattering*, $|S_{HH}| \approx |S_{VV}| \approx |S_{HV}|$, characteristic of heterogeneous media such as vegetation [27, 28].

Figure 7: Scattering types.

The interpretation of these mechanisms, as well as their interaction with interferometric observables, is central to PolInSAR and the models developed in this work [33, 25, 24].

2.4.2 Measurement and Representation of Polarimetric Data

To acquire the full scattering matrix, PolSAR systems alternate between H and V polarization modes during transmission and record the echo in both channels during reception. This process enables the reconstruction of all four components S_{HH} , S_{HV} , S_{VH} , S_{VV} through signal encoding and demodulation [8, 9]. Depending on the operational configuration, three acquisitions modes are distinguished, *Full-pol*, in which the radar alternates transmission in H and V and receives in both, thus obtaining the full scattering matrix, *Dual-pol*, which acquires two channels, usually HH and HV , and *Single-pol*, where only one polarization combination is acquired, i.e., HH [10, 33].

In mono-static spaceborn sensors, such those in satellites like Radarsat-2, ALOS-PALSAR or SAOCOM, it is commonly assumed (13), allowing the scattering matrix to be rewritten as [33],

$$S_{HV} = S_{VS} \rightarrow S = \begin{bmatrix} S_{HH} & S_{HV} \\ S_{HV} & S_{VV} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

For advanced polarimetric processing, the scattering matrix is transformed into vectorial representations that facilitate the derivation of second-order statistics. A key representa-

tion is the Pauli vector k , which is useful for polarimetric decomposition [33],

$$k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} S_{HH} + S_{VV} \\ S_{HH} - S_{VV} \\ 2S_{HV} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

From which the Coherency Matrix is defined [33],

$$T = \langle k \cdot k^H \rangle, \quad (16)$$

and the Covariance Matrix [33],

$$C = \langle s \cdot s^H \rangle, \quad (17)$$

where $s = [S_{HH}, S_{HV}, S_{VV}]^T$ is the lexicographic vector, and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes spatial averaging or *multilooking* to reduce the speckle noise [9].

These matrices preserve the second order statistics of the scattering process and form the basis of polarimetric classification, decomposition and coherence optimization. In PolInSAR, they used to construct the interferometric coherency matrices T_{11}, T_{22}, T_{12} required for multi-polarization coherence analysis [25, 33, 24].

2.4.3 Polarimetric Interferometric Coherence

The central parameter is the polarimetric interferometric coherence, a complex generalization of the scalar coherence presented in (5) by introducing a polarization dependant formulation. For a given polarization projection vector \vec{p} , it can be expressed as [20],

$$\gamma(\vec{k}_z, \vec{p}) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N S_1^n(\vec{p}) \cdot [S_2^{n*}(\vec{p})]^*}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N |S_1^n(\vec{p})|^2} \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N |S_2^n(\vec{p})|^2}}, \quad (18)$$

where S_1^n and S_2^n are the complex backscattered signals from the two interferometric acquisitions projected onto the polarization direction \vec{p} and \vec{k}_z is the vertical wave vector, linked to the system's height sensitivity through the HoA.

This parameter can be understood as a multichannel function that represents the coherence measured under different polarization states. Its analysis allows for the exploration of the medium's structure and the optimization of the estimation of variables such as the height of the scattering volume.

Polarimetric analysis in interferometry enables the investigation of multiple polarization combinations for each SAR pixel, by projecting the interferometric signals onto different directions in the polarimetric space. To formalize this across all polarizations, the scattering vectors of both acquisitions are embedded into coherency matrices T_{11}, T_{22} and across coherency matrix T_{12} . For any polarization vector $\vec{w} \in \mathbb{C}$, the projected interferometric coherence becomes [20],

$$\gamma(\vec{w}) = \frac{\vec{w}^H \cdot T_{12} \cdot \vec{w}}{\sqrt{\vec{w}^H \cdot T_{11} \cdot \vec{w}} \sqrt{\vec{w}^H \cdot T_{22} \cdot \vec{w}}}. \quad (19)$$

Where \vec{w}^H is the Hermitian transpose of \vec{w} . As seen in (18) and (19), \vec{p} is linked to the scattering matrix notation and \vec{w} with the coherency matrix. Based on this formulation, it is possible to get an optimization over polarimetric space, deriving the directions of maximum and minimum coherence. These directions are determined by solving the following generalized eigenvalue problem [20],

$$T_{12}\vec{w} = \gamma T_{11}\vec{w}, \quad (20)$$

whose solutions identify the optimal polarimetric projections. The corresponding eigenvalues approximate the maximum coherence γ_{max} , typically related to the ground response, and the minimum coherence, γ_{min} , associated with the most incoherent volume scattering. This process is known as coherence decomposition or coherence optimization [26].

This decomposition provides physical insight into the vertical structure of the scene and under the assumptions of two later scattering, it enables the empirical approximation, $\gamma_{max} \approx \gamma_{ground}$ and $\gamma_{min} \approx \gamma_{volume}$, which bounds the coherence region. In this region, coherence values can be interpolated or fitted using physical models to retrieve canopy height, ground to volume ratios or other forest parameters.

These capabilities are fully realized when PolInSAR is combined with scattering models such as RVoG [17, 25] or its temporal extension, RMoG [24]. These models allow for a physical interpretation of the observed coherence and enable more accurate parameter estimation of parameters. The combination of multichannel observation (i.e., multiple polarizations) with interferometric information helps resolve the ambiguity between volume and ground contributions and makes it possible to distinguish between different types of vegetation or phenological states, as will be discussed in the following sections.

In terms of applications, PolInSAR has been successfully used in missions such as ALOS-PALSAR and TanDEM-X, enabling accurate estimation of canopy height without the need for LiDAR data [17], structural classification of different types of vegetation or land cover and detection of phenological changes or wind and moisture effects, particularly when combined with RMoG. Owing to its ability to separate interferometric contributions based on their physical origin, PolInSAR is a fundamental tool in forest remote sensing, providing a detailed and quantifiable description of the forest's vertical structure.

2.5 Random Volume over Ground Model

The RVoG is a model of polarimetric coherence behavior in forest and arises from the need to more realistically represent forest environments in interferometric analyses. Unlike the conventional flat-earth model, RVoG accounts for volume scattering caused by vegetation and distinguishes it from the specular reflection originating from the ground [25]. This capability is essential for accurately estimating forest canopy height, as well as for assessing above-ground biomass and generating vegetation height maps (Canopy Height Models) [29, 31].

2.5.1 Physical Concept

The RVoG model provides a physically consistent description of radar backscatter in vegetated areas by considering the two main electromagnetic scattering mechanisms, the specular reflection from the ground and the volume scattering from the canopy.

From a physical perspective, the SAR return in a forest environment does not originate from a single reflective surface—as it might in open or urban areas—but rather results from multiple interactions between the radar signal and vegetation elements such as leaves, branches, and trunks, as well as the underlying terrain surface. The RVoG model assumes that these mechanisms can be coherently represented through the combination of two fundamental components [25, 26]:

- **Ground Component:** Corresponds to the signal directly reflected by the terrain surface. This reflection is specular in nature, following a relatively direct round-trip path, which results in a signal with high coherence. The phase of this signal is typically associated with a single elevation level, corresponding to the forest floor.
- **Volume Component:** Refers to the signal randomly scattered by the forest canopy. These structures act as distributed scatterers with no specific vertical order, generating a signal that propagates, attenuates, and reflects across various layers. Due to this heterogeneous distribution, the resulting signal exhibits lower coherence and a more diffuse phase compared to the ground component [17, 27].

This model assumes that the forest volume has a vertically homogeneous structure and that the scatterers are randomly distributed. This assumption enables a mathematical formulation of the volume backscatter behavior, introducing the extinction coefficient σ , which regulates the attenuation of the signal throughout the canopy. AS the signal penetrates the vegetation, its intensity decreases exponentially, thereby modulating the volumetric contribution to the interferometric coherence.

On the other hand, the use of Polarimetric Interferometry enhances the separation of ground and volume components. This is possible because different SAR polarizations exhibit varying sensitivities to scattering mechanisms [26, 31]. Generally, co-polarized channels (HH and VV) tend to better capture the signal reflected from the ground, whereas cross-polarized channels (HV and VH) are more sensitive to volume scattering. This differential behavior allows for the application of polarimetric optimization techniques to extract the maximum coherence associated with both volume and ground contributions,

substantially improving forest height estimation and the separation of the two contributions in the interferometric coherence [17, 28].

2.5.2 Coherence Modeling

The mathematical formulation that describes how ground and volume scattering combine lies at the core of the RVoG model. This model allows the total interferometric coherence to be expressed as a complex combination of both contributions, serving as the foundation for estimating forest structural parameters from PolInSAR data [25, 26]. As previously discussed, the model assumes that the total radar return is a weighted combination of signals originating from the vegetation volume and the ground. Accordingly, the total interferometric coherence can be expressed by the following equation [20],

$$\gamma_{\text{total}} = \frac{\mu_v \gamma_v + \mu_g \gamma_g e^{j\phi_g}}{\mu_v + \mu_g}, \quad (21)$$

where μ_v and μ_g are the relative weights of the volume and ground components, respectively that is, the intensity with which each contributes to the total signal. γ_v is the coherence of the volume, and γ_g is the coherence of the ground, which is typically assumed to be close to 1, as it corresponds to a specular and stable surface. ϕ_g is the phase difference between the ground and the volume components. As can be seen, this model captures the fact that both volume and ground contribute simultaneously to the radar return, each with its own distinct phase, thereby influencing the total coherence measured by the system.

The volume coherence, γ_v , is particularly important and is modeled as the Fourier transform of the vertical scattering profile, $P(z)$. Its general form is [20],

$$\gamma_v = \frac{\int_0^h P(z) \cdot e^{-2jk_z z} dz}{\int_0^h P(z) dz}, \quad (22)$$

where h is the forest height, k_z is the vertical component of the wavenumber vector (which depends on the SAR system geometry), and the function $P(z)$ represents the vertical distribution of scatterer density. If we assume a normalized exponential profile, random scatterers decreasing with height, that is [17],

$$P(z) = \frac{\sigma e^{-\sigma z}}{1 - e^{-\sigma h}}. \quad (23)$$

Where σ controls the attenuation of the signal as it propagates through the canopy. Substituting into equation (22) and solving, we obtain [17],

$$\gamma_v = \frac{\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma + 2jk_z}\right)(1 - e^{-h(\sigma + 2jk_z)})}{1 - e^{-\sigma h}}, \quad (24)$$

which, by multiplying both the numerator and denominator by $\frac{1}{\sigma}$, leads to one of the most compact and widely used closed-form expressions [20],

$$\gamma_v = \frac{1 - e^{-h(\sigma + 2jk_z)}}{(1 - e^{-\sigma h})(1 + \frac{2jk_z}{\sigma})}. \quad (25)$$

These expressions allow a direct relationship to be established between forest height and the observed coherence. As the canopy height increases, coherence decreases due to greater attenuation and destructive interference among multiple scatterers.

In some alternative formulations, particularly when uniform scattering is assumed or analytical approximations are applied, an algebraically equivalent written form can be derived. This expression arises when a uniform distribution of scatterers is considered (i.e., $P(z) = cte.$), or when terms are simplified under the assumption of low extinction and expanded using a Taylor series approximation [17],

$$\gamma_v = e^{-\sigma h} \frac{1 - e^{-2jk_z h}}{2jk_z h}. \quad (26)$$

Both forms mentioned are consistent with the theoretical framework of the model but rely on different assumptions. The first expression (25), is more general and accurate, while the second is simpler and more suitable for fast numerical implementations.

Another commonly used algebraic reformulation of the same expression is [17],

$$\gamma_v = \frac{e^{h(\sigma + ik_z)} - 1}{(e^{h\sigma} - 1)(1 + ik_z/\sigma)}, \quad (27)$$

which is obtained through algebraic manipulation by integrating $P(z) = \sigma^{-\sigma z}$, and represents the same formulation but expressed in terms of exponential growth rather than decay.

Figure 8: Volume Coherence $|\gamma_v|$ vs. Canopy Height h_v , for Different Values of the Extinction Coefficient σ .

These formulas, although physically rigorous, involve expressions with complex exponentials and relative weight proportions that can complicate numerical fitting. For this reason,

in practice, the equations are often reformulated using an equivalent parameter M , which represents the ratio between the energy reflected by the ground and the energy scattered by the volume. This parameter is defined as [20],

$$M = \left| \frac{\mu_g}{\mu_v} \right|^2, \quad (28)$$

This substitution allows the total coherence expression to be written in a more operational form [20],

$$\gamma_{total} = e^{i\phi_g} \cdot [(\gamma_v - 1) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{M} \cdot e^{h\sigma}} \right) + 1]. \quad (29)$$

This set of expressions, although algebraically equivalent to the initial theoretical formulas, (21) and (26), offers a significant advantage by facilitating numerical fitting through functions that require only observable variables h and k_z , along with the model parameters M , σ and ϕ_g as inputs.

This model enables a physical interpretation of the observed coherence and its sensitivity to structural changes in the forest. As illustrated in Figure 8, the magnitude of γ_v decreases with increasing canopy height for fixed values of σ . This behavior underpins the RVoG model inversion techniques, where the observed coherence is fitted to theoretical curves in order to estimate forest height [17, 31].

This set of expressions has been implemented computationally in this work, as detailed in Chapter 3, enabling parametric sweeps and efficient fitting of the model's three main parameters. The simplified formulation has proven to preserve the physical rigor of the original model while enhancing its practical applicability.

In the modeling plots presented throughout this study, forest height is commonly shown on the horizontal axis as a fraction of the interferometric height of ambiguity (h/HoA) introduced in [17] and presented in Figure 8. The use of this ratio enables normalization of canopy height relative to the vertical sensitivity of the SAR system, which is particularly useful for comparing results across different geometric configurations or satellite missions [25]. Moreover, this dimensionless scaling facilitates the interpretation of interferometric behavior, as coherence curves exhibit a characteristic decay with respect to this variable, more stable and generalizable than when using absolute height values [24]. Therefore, h/HoA serves as a metric that is consistent with the system's vertical resolution and is a common reference in the specialized literature for the representation and analysis of models such as RVoG or RMoG.

2.5.3 Practical Application of the RVoG Model

The RVoG model not only provides a solid theoretical framework for interpreting radar signal behavior in forested environments, but it is also widely applicable in real-world contexts for estimating forest structural parameters [25, 31]. In practice, the model parameters are estimated through inversion processes that compare the observed interferometric coherence in different polarizations with those predicted by the theoretical model.

This comparison enables the estimation, at pixel or regional level, of the main biophysical forest parameters, h , σ , and M .

Model inversion is carried out using nonlinear fitting techniques or statistical methods, such as least squares, gradient descent optimization, or Bayesian approaches, which allows for the exploration of the parameter space and the identification of the optimal combination that best reproduces the observations [17, 28].

Once the parameters are estimated from observations, it becomes possible to generate continuous forest height maps, known as Canopy Height Models (CHMs), directly from SAR data. This capability is particularly valuable, as it enables large-scale structural analysis of forest without the need for auxiliary data. While external references such as LiDAR data, forest inventories, or digital elevation models can be used for validation and calibration, the RVoG model allows for autonomous estimations from PolInSAR data alone, making it an effective tool for forest monitoring in remote or data-scarce regions [16, 29].

The RVoG model has been successfully validated in numerous space missions operating in canopy-penetrating frequency bands, such as L-band. Notable examples include TanDEM-X, which employs Bistatic configurations to acquire high-resolution polarimetric coherence [17], ALOS-PALSAR, a Japanese mission that has provided L-band PolInSAR data over extensive forested areas, and BIOMASS, an upcoming European Space Agency (ESA) mission specifically designed for biomass and forest height estimation, which adopts the RVoG model as a reference in its inversion algorithms [24].

Although the RVoG model is based on certain simplifications discussed earlier, such as the assumption of a homogeneous and static volume, its results have proven sufficiently accurate for a wide range of operational applications. However, in scenarios where these assumptions do not hold, such as in heterogeneous forest or environments with high temporal variability, the model may present limitations.

To address these cases, the RMoG model has been developed. It introduces temporal decorrelation in both the volume and the ground as additional factors, and will be presented in the following section.

2.6 Random Motion over Ground Model

The RMoG model emerges as an extension of the RVoG model, where RVoG models polarimetric coherence for single pass interferometry, RMoG models polarimetric coherence for repeat pass interferometry. Designed to more accurately represent dynamic forest environments where significant structural changes occur between interferometric acquisitions [24]. Unlike RVoG, which assumes a static volume during the acquisition interval, RMoG incorporates the possibility of random internal movements within the canopy, such as those caused by wind, vegetative growth, phenological variation, or mechanical displacement of leaves and branches.

This movements introduce additional temporal decorrelation that cannot be accounted for by the classical model. This coherence loss is especially evident in regions with high biological activity or variable weather conditions, such as tropical forest or wetlands, where the canopy structure changes noticeably between acquisitions. RMoG's ability to represent this temporal structural variability makes it a key tool for improving forest height estimation under non-ideal conditions.

2.6.1 Physical Concept

The physical foundation of the RMoG model lies in introducing an additional source of interferometric decorrelation associated with internal motion within the forest volume. This coherence loss is not due to geometric changes or the structure of the volume itself, but rather to dynamic modifications of the environment between SAR acquisitions.

The model does not aim to represent the exact motion of each scatterer, instead, it introduces a global penalty term on the volume coherence from the RVoG model. This penalization is linked to the degree of structural variation in the canopy and depends on both the intensity of the motion and the radar's vertical resolution, determined by the vertical wavenumber component k_z .

2.6.2 Coherence Modeling

The RMoG model extends the RVoG formulation by explicitly incorporating the effect of temporal decorrelation associated with random internal motion within the vegetation between the two interferometric acquisitions. This additional contribution is statistically modeled as a penalization term applied to the volume coherence, allowing for a more accurate representation of coherence loss observe in forested environments [24]. The coherence loss due to random motion of scatterers within the volume can be represented by a Gaussian vertical displacement between acquisitions, with zero mean and variance σ_{disp}^2 . Under this assumption, the penalization term that quantifies the coherence loss due to motion, denoted as δ_{motion} , is defined as [24],

$$\sigma_{motion} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot k_z^2 \cdot \sigma_{disp}^2, \quad (30)$$

where k_z remains the vertical component of the wavenumber vector, which depends on the SAR geometry and the radar wavelength. This term reveals that coherence loss increases

with both the vertical sensitivity of the SAR system and the intensity of the internal displacement.

The combined effect of volume scattering, ground reflection, and internal motion is represented through an exponential penalization applied to the coherence of the RVoG model as [24],

$$\gamma_{RMoG} = \gamma_{RVoG} \cdot e^{-\delta_{motion}}. \quad (31)$$

This expression implies that greater structural variability within the canopy or higher vertical resolution leads to increased interferometric coherence loss.

Just as with the RVoG model, the theoretical expression of the RMoG model can be reformulated to facilitate its computational implementation. Analogous to the approach used in the RVoG model, the volume coherence (25) is modified as follows [24],

$$\gamma_v = \frac{e^{h(\sigma + ik_z)} - 1}{(e^{h\sigma} - 1)(1 + ik_z/\sigma)} \cdot e^{-\sigma_V}, \quad (32)$$

where σ_V represents the volume-specific temporal decorrelation. This term attenuates the estimated coherence as a consequence of structural fluctuations within the canopy.

Subsequently, the ground contribution is also adapted, incorporating a similar penalization to account for potential temporal decorrelation at the ground level,

$$G_T = \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{M} \cdot e^{h\sigma}} \right) \cdot e^{-\sigma_G}, \quad (33)$$

where σ_G represents the temporal decorrelation of the ground between acquisitions, and M is still the ratio between the reflected powers from the ground and the volume, as introduced earlier. Finally, the expression for the total coherence in the RMoG model is given by

$$\gamma_{total} = e^{i\phi_g} \cdot [(\gamma_v - 1) \cdot G_T + 1]. \quad (34)$$

This reformulation offers greater computational efficiency in real-world applications, while preserving the physical foundation of the original model. It enables the operational use of the RMoG model for forest height estimation in dynamic environments [24].

Figure 9: Behavior of the RMoG Model for Different Displacement Values.

The incorporation of temporal decorrelation in both layers, volume and ground, allows correction of biases observed in height estimates obtained using the classical RVoG model. In particular, it has been shown that even small losses of temporal coherence can induce significant biases, especially in low-stature forests, making compensation essential for achieving reliable estimations [24]. Moreover, the model adapts to different acquisition regimes, from short baselines to several days of temporal separation, adjusting its behavior to the actual physical changes observed in experimental campaigns such as BioSAR or TempoSAR [24].

As in the case of the RVoG model, coherence is represented as a function of the normalized height h/HoA , which enables a consistent visualization of the effect of temporal decorrelation introduced by the RMoG model. This normalization for the RMoG is the first time done and facilitates direct comparison between different acquisition settings and helps isolate the influence of internal canopy motion on the coherence decay pattern.

2.6.3 Practical Application of the RMoG model

The RMoG model is particularly valuable in situations where vegetation undergoes significant structural dynamics between interferometric acquisitions, such as, humid tropical forests, where growth rates, phenological activity, and transpiration vary rapidly, ecosystems affected by changing weather conditions, including wind, heavy rainfall, or moisture-dryness cycles. Long-term monitoring studies, where the time interval between acquisitions may span weeks or months or seasonal transitions, such as boreal snowmelt or autumnal changes, where canopy structure evolves quickly.

In all these contexts, it is common for the observed interferometric coherence to be lower than that predicted by the RVoG model, due to temporal decorrelation caused by internal volume motion. Applying the RMoG model allows this loss to be compensated for by

explicitly integrating the dynamic effect, resulting in more accurate estimations of forest height and structural parameters [24].

The inversion process of the RMoG model is similar to that of RVoG, it involves adjusting the model parameters so that the predicted coherence matches the observed one. However, it introduces the additional parameter σ_{dips}^2 , which must be either estimated directly from the data, if repeated acquisitions are available, assumed or bounded based on vegetation type, season, or expected climatic conditions or empirically calibrated using auxiliary data sources. This flexibility allows the model to adapt to a wider range of conditions, which is especially important for operational applications in tropical or remote regions where acquisition conditions can vary significantly [17, 28].

2.7 RVoG vs. RMoG Comparison

The main difference between the RVoG and RMoG models lies in how they handle the temporal behavior of the volume. While the RVoG model assumes a static and homogeneous volume between acquisitions, the RMoG model introduces the possibility of random internal motion within the forest canopy, thereby incorporating an additional temporal decorrelation component that directly affects the interferometric coherence.

This enhancement enables the RMoG model to adapt to environments with high structural variability, such as tropical and humid forests, or those exposed to extreme weather conditions, where vegetation undergoes significant changes over short time periods, as in [17] the normalization concept is extended to RMoG in order to compare both models.

Table 2: RVoG vs. RMoG

Characteristic	RVoG	RMoG
Dispersion type	Volume + Ground	Volume + Ground with random movement
Volume Representation	Static	Dynamic (temporal structural variation)
Consider internal movement	No	Yes
Volumetric coherence	Attenuated by extinction	Attenuated by extinction and temporal decorrelation
Applications	Stable or Boreal Forests	Tropical, Humid, or High-Variability Forests

Table 10 presents a summary comparison of the main characteristics of both models. Meanwhile, Figure 10 illustrates a comparison between the volume coherence curves estimated by each model. For the same canopy height, the RMoG model predicts lower coherence values than the RVoG model. This difference is due to the additional coherence loss caused by internal volume motion, which is captured by the δ_{motion} term in the RMoG model.

Figure 10: RVoG vs. RMoG comparison.

This effect is particularly noticeable when the variance of internal displacement σ_{disp} is high, as occurs in areas with high humidity, strong winds, or intense biological activity. Therefore, in practical applications where the measured coherence is significantly lower than that predicted by the RVoG model, incorporating the RMoG model enables improved accuracy in forest height estimations [17, 28].

2.8 Pearson Correlation

To assess the relationship between observed variables, such as forest canopy height and interferometric coherence, Pearson correlation has been used as the primary statistical tool. It is a statistical measure that evaluates the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient, denoted as r , is defined by the following expression,

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}}, \quad (35)$$

where x_i and y_i are the individual values of the variables, \bar{x} and \bar{y} their respective means, and the summations cover all sample values. This coefficient ranges from -1 to 1. A value close to 1 indicates a strong positive correlation, i.e., as one variable increases, so does the other. A value close to 0 suggests no linear relationship between the variables, and a value close to -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, i.e., as one variable increases, the other decreases. From a statistical perspective, the numerator of the equation (35) represents the covariance between the two variables,

$$Cov(X, Y) = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{n - 1}. \quad (36)$$

While the denominator normalizes the covariance by dividing it by the product of the standard deviations of the variables, ensuring that r is dimensionless and remains within the range $[-1, 1]$.

This tool is widely used in quantitative data analysis due to its simplicity and effectiveness in identifying linear patterns. However, it is important to note that it does not capture non-linear relationships and is sensitive to outliers, which can significantly influence the result and affect the interpretation of the correlation. For this reason, its application in the present work has been complemented by visual inspection of scatter plots and class-based analyses, in order to correctly interpret the observed trends between interferometric coherence and forest structural parameters.

3 Models Evaluation

3.1 Datasets Used

3.1.1 TanDEM-X Dataset

For the following sections, one of the datasets used consist of interferometric data acquired through the TanDEM-X mission. This mission, developed by the German Aerospace Center (DLR), is composed of two twin satellites operating in Bistatic interferometric mode, enabling the simultaneous acquisition of SAR images with high coherence and spatial resolution. This approach eliminates the effects of temporal decorrelation, ensuring high-quality interferometric measurements [17].

The data used in this thesis include geocoded polarimetric interferometric pairs, containing both coherence information and polarimetric covariance matrices required for physical modeling using the RVoG framework [25]. These products were processed from StripMap mode scenes, acquired in Bistatic configuration between 2010 and 2012. Only the HH polarization was used to ensure consistency between acquisitions, since, as demonstrated in previous studies [18], differences with VV polarization are minimal under non-flooded conditions.

The selected study areas are two representative forest regions located in Estonia, Järvelja (within the Peipsiveere Nature Reserve) and Soomaa National Park. These areas exhibit contrasting structural and ecological conditions, making them ideal sites for the analysis of interferometric coherence in heterogeneous forest environments [17].

- **Järvelja-Peipsiveere** features a wide variety of forest species, predominantly Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), silver birch (*Betula pendula*) and Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), distributed across a relatively flat and homogeneous environment, although wetland and riparian zones are also present.
- **Soomaa** is characterized by extensive wetlands and more dynamic mixed forest. The dominant species range from conifers to broadleaf trees, including deciduous vegetation such as black and grey alder (*Alnus glutinosa* and *Alnus incana*), and aspen (*Populus tremula*), enabling a differentiated analysis based on forest cover type.

Both regions exhibit flat topographic conditions, which reduces geometric distortions in the SAR signal and improves the reliability of model fitting [28]. The SAR images were acquired under different incident angles and with varying heights of ambiguity, allowing for the assessment of the impact of these parameters on the sensitivity of the coherence model.

Figure 11: Geographic location of the study areas in Estonia. The area of Soomaa National Park is highlighted in red, and the Järvselja region is marked in blue.

Complementarily, reference data obtained through airborne LiDAR scanning (ALS) were available. These data were provided by the Estonian Land Board and processed using the P90 metric of the echo height profile, which is considered to be highly correlated with the actual forest canopy height. The LiDAR resolution was 0.45 points/m^2 , and a Digital Terrain Model (DMT) was used as the base for calculating relative heights [23].

The correspondence between LiDAR data and SAR imagery was established through a rigorous process of orthorectification and geocoding, using orbital metadata and digital terrain models. Subsequently, analysis polygons were defined based on the boundaries of homogeneous forest stands, extracted from the official buffer was applied to each polygon (20 m in Soomaa and 15 m in Järvselja)

Finally, a specific selection of forest stands was carried out based on criteria of homogeneity, presence of a single dominant species, absence of understory, and a minimum area of 1 ha. This meticulous preparation enabled a robust and reliable analysis of the relationship between interferometric coherence and forest height.

Taken together, this integrated dataset constitutes a solid and representative experimental framework for validating the theoretical model hypothesis and evaluating its performance under real field conditions, both by forest type and geographic zone [24].

3.1.2 Sentinel-1 Dataset

The second dataset used in this study correspond to the Kotka region, in southeastern Finland, and combines interferometric SAR observations from the Sentinel-1 mission with ALS data and in situ forest plot measurements.

Sentinel-1 is a C-band radar mission under the ESA Copernicus program, consisting of two identical satellites, Sentinel-1A and Sentinel-1B, operating in a repeat-pass configuration. It provides global coverage with high temporal frequency and excellent geometric stability [19, 42]. The images used for this analysis were acquired in Interferometric Wide Swath (IW) mode, which offers a spatial resolution of approximately 10 m in both azimuth and range, with a 12-day revisit interval [40].

For this study, pairs of Sentinel-1 images acquired in 2021 were selected in both ascending and descending configurations, in order to assess the geometric effects on interferometric coherence. The system geometry in the Kotka region yields an average height of ambiguity of approximately 42 m, providing an intermediate vertical sensitivity suitable for analyzing boreal forest structures ranging from 10 to 35 m in height [17].

The interferograms were generated from Single Look Complex (SLC) products downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub. The interferometric processing included precise co-registration between master and slave images using cross-correlation techniques, adaptive filtering to reduce phase noise, and the computation of complex interferometric coherence using 7x7 pixel windows [2, 4]. The resulting coherence values were then geocoded and aligned with the reference LiDAR model. The ground reference is based on the CHM developed by the Finnish Forest Center with a resolution of 1 m, derived from regressions on ALS data and field sampling [23]. DEM and relative height models were used to compute canopy height and to align SAR data with field observations.

Figure 12: Analysis area in the Kotka region.

The study area, shown in Figure 12, covers a mixed forest region composed of both coniferous and deciduous species, including *Pinus sylvestris*, *Picea abies*, *Betula spp.*,

Alnus spp., and *Populus tremula*, A total of over 300 field plots are available, evenly distributed across the area, each associated with a set of biophysical variables such as mean height, timber volume, and basal area. The topography in Kotka is predominantly flat or gently undulating, which minimizes geometric phase errors in interferometry. However, the use of Sentinel-1 in repeat-pass configuration inevitably introduces temporal decorrelation, which is explicitly accounted for by applying the RMoG model instead of the RVoG model, as discussed in the following sections [24, 37].

3.2 Relationship Between Interferometric Coherence, Phase and Height

An initial exploratory correlation analysis was conducted prior to applying the physical models for forest height estimation described in the previous chapters. The objective was to empirically validate the theoretical relationships between the interferometric variables (coherence and phase) and forest height. This preliminary step is essential to confirm the foundation of the RVoG model, which posits that volume scattering associated with greater canopy height leads to a progressive loss of coherence and a shift in the scattering centroid that affects the interferometric phase [33, 35, 36].

In general terms, the Pearson correlation between coherence and forest height is negative and moderately strong, $r = -0.611$. This relationship is more pronounced in Järvelja, $r = -0.822$ and less intense in Soomaa, $r = -0.441$. This difference can be attributed to the structural and dynamic forest variations previously discussed [29, 41].

Table 3: Correlation Between Height and Interferometric Variables by Region.

Region	Coherence vs. Height	Phase vs. Height
Järvelja	$r=-0.822$	$r=-0.621$
Soomaa	$r=-0.441$	$r=-0.711$

Similarly, the correlation between interferometric phase and forest height also exhibits a negative trend, with an overall value of $r = -0.68$, further supporting the hypothesis that both variables provide key structural information [26, 28]. In this case, Järvelja shows a weaker correlation, $r = -0.621$, compared to Soomaa, $r = -0.711$. This results are summarized in Table 3, moreover, when the data are segmented by forest species type, a similar trend is observed, as shown in Table ??.

Table 4: Correlation Between Height and Interferometric Variables by Region.

Forest Type	Coherence vs. Height	Phase vs. Height
Pine	$r=-0.6$	$r=-0.86$
Spruce	$r=-0.73$	$r=-0.76$
Deciduous	$r=-0.59$	$r=-0.59$

These results support the conclusion that there is a consistent empirical relationship between interferometric variables and canopy height, validating the use of coherence and phase as structural indicators in estimation models such as RVoG and RMoG [25, 37].

Figure 13: Interferometric Coherence vs. Forest Height.

Figure 14: Interferometric Phase vs. Forest Height.

Figures 13 and 14 present visual representations of the relationship between the variables using the entire dataset, along with the corresponding trend lines. Complementary plot and analyses are provided in Annex 5.1, where each region and forest type is examined in greater detail.

3.3 Model Fitting and Evaluation

Having empirically demonstrated that both interferometric coherence and phase are related to forest canopy height, the next step is to apply the physical models described in the theoretical framework. The objective of this section is to evaluate the ability of these models to reproduce the vertical structure of the forest through inversion techniques, as well as to analyze their accuracy and robustness across different forest environments. To this end, parametric fitting procedures were carried out to compare the interferometric coherence predicted by the model with real data, both in terms of magnitude, in the complex plane, and in interferometric phase.

3.3.1 Parameter Fitting for the RVoG Model

Once the model was implemented, a practical fitting was performed using real data acquired through interferometric SAR. The following sections present visual comparisons between the observed data and the model-generated curves.

The physical RVoG model used for forest height estimation is based on three main parameters, canopy height, the volume extinction coefficient and the ground-to-volume power ratio. For each forest stand or sample set analyzed, these parameters were adjusted through an iterative process that minimizes the root mean square error (RMSE) between the observed and the model-predicted interferometric coherence. This fitting was carried out sequentially by keeping two parameters fixed while optimizing the third, in a stepwise process that converges toward an optimal parameter combination.

In this fitting process, the interferometric ground phase ϕ_g was not treated as a free parameter. In the model formulation, this term represents the phase offset between the volume and ground contributions, and it can influence the complex shape of the coherence. However, in scenarios where the ground lies at the base of the vertical coordinate system, as is the case here, it is expected that $\phi_g = 0$. Allowing this parameter to vary freely may lead to non-physical solutions or results inconsistent with the geometry of the problem. For this reason, $\phi_g = 0$ was fixed throughout the entire fitting process, in accordance with standard practice in similar applications [24, 25].

Another important aspect observed during the analysis is that the theoretical interferometric coherence predicted by the model starts from a unitary value, $|\gamma| = 1$, when $h = 0$, that is, when the scattering originates exclusively from the ground. However, in the experimental data, initial coherence values are typically lower, often around 0.9 or even less. This discrepancy is due to systematic signal degradation effects, represented by the $\gamma_{baseline}$ term discussed in Section 2.1 [32]. This initial deviation is consistent with previous studies, where a reduced baseline coherence value is observed even under ideal conditions with negligible volume contribution [28].

First, the ground-to-volume ratio, M , was adjusted. In this first approximation, a constant value was set for the extinction coefficient, $\sigma = 0.01$, and for the interferometric ground phase, $\phi = 0$. This allows for an isolated assessment of how the volume-to-ground ratio influences the shape of the coherence curve. Figure 15 shows the absolute value of the interferometric coherence estimated by the model for different values of M , along with

the observed data.

Figure 15: Behavior of the RVoG Model for Different Values of M Over the Measured Samples.

During the fitting process, it was found that the value ($M \approx 1.4$), provides a reasonable approximation for a large number of samples, accurately reproducing the coherence decay as a function of normalized height. However, this value cannot be considered mathematically optimal in a general sense, as the model may be influenced by noisy samples, labeling errors or unrepresentative geometry. This introduces uncertainty in the fitting process, especially if robust filtering or appropriate weighting of the samples is not applied. As a result, the reliability of the fit relies more on its structural validity and the visual quality of the match than on a pure numerical minimization of the error [17, 29].

Figure 16 shows the curves for different values of σ .

Figure 16: Behavior of the RVoG Model for Different Values of σ Over the Measured Samples.

It is observed that variations in this parameter in this parameter primary affect the slope and amplitude of the curve. As shown, increasing the extinction coefficient results in greater attenuation of the volume signal, smoothing the coherence decay and shifting the curve's minimum. The visual fit suggest a value of $\sigma \approx 0.01$, which is consistent with typical values for dense forest stands.

This combination has proven to provide the best visual and quantitative fit to the measured data, offering a robust foundation for the subsequent inversion of forest height.

Figure 17: RVoG Model Fitted to Interferometric Coherence.

The results obtained show that the properly fitted RVoG model is capable of accurately reproducing the observed interferometric behavior in forested environments. This validation of the model across multiple regions and forest types ensures its robustness and physical consistency. This model provides a solid foundation for the subsequent implementation of the RMoG model, which will extend the analysis capability to environments with temporal changes or high structural dynamics.

3.3.2 Parameter Fitting for the RMoG Model

Once the RVoG model has been adjusted and validated using the dataset from Jarvselja and Soomaa in section 3.3.1, we extend the analysis by incorporating the effects of temporal decorrelation due to internal motion within the scattering volume and ground. This leads to the RMoG model, which accounts for additional coherence loss caused by uncontrolled micro-movements of scatterers between acquisitions.

As explained in Section 2.5, the RMoG model introduces two exponential decorrelation terms that attenuate the observed coherence, σ_v and σ_g , that are the temporal decorrelation coefficients associated with movement within volume and ground surface, respectively. These coefficients represent the rate at which coherence is lost due to temporal effects and are applied multiplicatively to the RVoG coherence prediction.

The fitting strategy goes as follows. Rather than performing full nonlinear optimization, we maintain the previously estimated parameters $M = 1.4$ and $\sigma = 0.01$ from the RVoG fit and analyze the impact of different values of σ_v and σ_g on the coherence-height relationship. As previously, each combination is evaluated using the average kz and HoA, over a synthetic profile of normalized canopy heights.

Figure 18 shows the impact of increasing σ_v . As we can see, the value that aligns the best with our dataset is $\sigma_v \approx 0.12$.

Figure 18: RMoG model adjusted to the measured coherence using multiple values of σ_v

As expected, increasing σ_v uniformly reduces coherence across the height range. The curve becomes increasingly shifted downward, matching the lower bounds of the observed data. The behavior aligns with the hypothesis of structural movement within the canopy, particularly in periods of environmental variability.

Figure 19 illustrates the role of σ_g , representing decorrelation at the ground layer. Maintaining the value of $\sigma_v = 0.12$, we see that $\sigma_g \approx 0.05$ represents the best fit for the model.

Figure 19: RMoG model fitted with varying values of σ_g .

In this case, the effect is non-uniform and more visible at larger heights, where the contribution of ground scattering dominates. Increasing σ_g results in a significant reduction of the asymptotic coherence, helping to explain residual differences between the RVoG prediction and the observed data in the high canopy regime.

The RMoG model introduces physical realism by acknowledging that the scene is not static. Even in the absence of structural changes, small displacements due to wind, temperature, moisture or system noise can significantly degrade the observed coherence.

As a final step, Figure 20 presents a direct comparison between the models fitted.

Figure 20: Comparison between the RVoG and RMoG model fitted to the measured coherence.

While the RVoG accurately follows the initial coherence decay, it tends to overestimate coherence at intermediate heights and fails to reproduce the observed leveling off at higher canopy values. In contrast, the RMoG model achieves better alignment across the entire profile, particularly beyond $h/HoA > 0.4$. This highlights the value of explicitly modeling decorrelation effects, even when the structural parameters are well calibrated.

4 Sentinel-1 Dataset Results

Estimating vegetation height from SAR data requires a deep understanding of how canopy structure influences interferometric coherence. This section presents an additional analysis conducted over boreal regions in Norway, Sweden and Finland, using coherence data derived from Sentinel-1 interferometric pairs, along with vegetation height references from ICESat-2 and airborne LiDAR (ALS).

The main objective is to assess the correlation between interferometric coherence, in both HV and VV channels, and forest height, under varying acquisition conditions, dates, seasons, incidence angle and kz . In addition, the temporal stability and structural consistency of SAR signal behavior are analyzed. To this end, descriptive analyses, multivariate exploration and structured outlier filtering based on physical criteria were conducted, including fitting to the RVoG model.

The results complement and contrast the findings obtained in the mixed forest of Estonia, providing a broader view of the applicability of PolInSAR models in real-world scenarios and highlighting the importance of selecting reliable samples before proceeding with model fitting.

4.1 Temporal and Seasonal Exploration

This section presents an exploratory analysis of the relationship between interferometric coherence and canopy height under varying acquisition conditions. The analysis was performed on datasets from Sweden, Norway and Finland. The objective is to assess whether consistent structural patterns or seasonal trends can be observed in the coherence signal, which could support its use in forest height estimation frameworks.

The analysis was structured along five main axes, by acquisition date, assessing intra-seasonal and inter-annual variability, by season, grouping data into spring, summer and autumn to capture phenological effects. By canopy height, satisfying data into 3 meters intervals to explore structural dependencies, by incidence angle, to assess how geometry affects coherence-height relationships, and by kz , which reflects the sensitivity of interferometric geometry to vertical structure. In addition, correlation matrices were computed for each region and season to quantify the relationship between coherence and canopy height under different temporal scenarios.

This work covers the full range of visual and statistical analyses performed. However, only a selected subset of the most representative figures is included in this section to facilitate interpretation and avoid redundancy. The complete set of visualizations is provided in Annex 5.1 for reference.

Each of the following sub-sections focuses on one geographical region, presenting the key findings that emerged from this multidimensional analysis.

4.1.1 Norway and Sweden

In the forested regions of Sweden and Norway, Sentinel-1 interferometric coherence data were analyzed in relation to canopy height derived from ICESat-2. The dataset spans several acquisition dates and covers wide range of seasonal and geometric conditions.

Figure 21 shows the distribution of all available samples in the coherence-height space, including the result of an unsupervised clustering algorithm.

Figure 21: Distribution of coherence and canopy height over Sweden and Norway, with clustering results.

The presence of multiple statistical groupings in the coherence-height space suggest the existence of underlying structural variability, although these clusters do not align directly with specific height classes. This indicates that coherence is influenced by additional factors beyond forest height alone.

To examine potential seasonal effects, coherence-height scatterplots were generated for representative dates. Figure 22 show one acquisition from autumn.

Figure 22: Coherence vs. canopy height over Sweden and Norway on September 28, 2024.

This figure illustrates the high intra-seasonal variability and the absence of a strong or consistent coherence degradation trend with increasing height. While some reduction in HV coherence is visible at intermediate heights, the effect is weak and highly scattered. This confirms a high degree of temporal variability.

Figure 23 summarizes the seasonal behavior by grouping the data into three seasons, spring, summer and autumn, as there is no data in winter, and comparing the resulting coherence distributions.

Figure 23: Seasonal coherence distribution grouped by spring, summer and autumn over Sweden and Norway.

Summer acquisitions tend to exhibit slightly higher and more stable coherence values, especially in the VV channel. This may be due to higher canopy density and lower temporal decorrelation during the growing season. However, the differences between seasons are not sharp and variability remains significant across all groups.

Finally, Figure 24 presents the correlation matrix computed over the entire dataset. The correlation coefficients between canopy height and coherence, for both channels, remain close to zero. This highlights the weak direct relationship between the two variables under under-filtered conditions.

Figure 24: Correlation Matrix between coherence and canopy height over Sweden and Norway.

In summary, the exploratory analysis in Sweden and Norway shows that although coherence varies across time and acquisition geometry, no strong or stable link to canopy height is evident. This reinforces the need for additional filtering or model based approaches to extract height sensitive coherence behavior, as further explored in later sections.

4.1.2 Finland

The Sentinel-1 dataset for the region of Kotka, Finland, provides a valuable test case for exploring temporal and structural variations in interferometric coherence. With over 40 acquisitions dates, the dataset offers a broader time range than in Sweden and Norway, enabling a more detailed examination of coherence behavior across vertical forest structure.

Figure 25, displays the full coherence-height distribution and clustering output for the Kotka region.

Figure 25: Distribution of coherence and canopy height over Finland, with clustering results.

As in the other sites, the data reveal high variability and overlapping clusters, without clear separation based on canopy height. This again suggest that coherence is driven by multiple factors and cannot be directly attributed to vertical structure alone.

Figure 26 presents coherence-height scatterplot of a representative date in summer.

Figure 26: Coherence vs. canopy height for acquisition over Finland on July 21, 2024.

The summer acquisition shows slightly tighter grouping and lower dispersion, particularly in the HV channel, suggesting higher temporal coherence stability in mature canopies. In contrast, the winter acquisitions show in Appendix 5.1 displays greater variability and lower coherence values, possibly due to changes in snow cover or vegetation conditions.

To assess broader seasonal effects, Figure 27 aggregates the data by season.

Figure 27: Seasonal distribution of coherence grouped by spring, summer and autumn over Finland.

As observed in the Swedish and Norwegian datasets, summer tends to yield slightly higher and more stable coherence in both channels. However, dispersion remains considerable and no robust seasonal signature emerges.

Finally, Figure 28 shows the correlation matrix for the Kotka dataset. As in the other regions, the correlation between coherence and canopy height remains low, confirming that raw coherence is not a reliable standalone predictor of forest height without additional filtering or modeling steps.

Figure 28: Correlation matrix between coherence and canopy height over Finland.

The results from Finland reinforce the patterns observed in other regions, although certain temporal and seasonal effects may influence coherence, its relationship with canopy height is weak and masked by noise, acquisition variability and structural heterogeneity. These findings support the need for advanced filtering strategies and physical modeling approaches to isolate height-sensitive coherence behavior.

4.2 Structural Validation and Coherence Filtering based on Models

The interpretation of interferometric coherence in vegetated areas depends not only on radar acquisition parameters but also on the structural and geometric characteristics of the forest. In this section, we evaluate the internal consistency between Sentinel-1 coherence and vegetation height in boreal forest environments using ALS as reference. The analysis focuses on the regions of Kotka and Joensuu in Finland, where dense time series of Sentinel-1 acquisitions are available.

This chapter has the aim of validating the accuracy of spaceborn height products against ALS, analyzing the relationship between coherence and canopy height under different conditions, characterizing temporal behavior of coherence metrics and applying a multi-criteria filtering strategy based on physical consistency with the RVoG model.

The final goal of this validation and filtering stage is to isolate a subset of samples that exhibit physically meaningful coherence patterns, suitable for subsequent model inversion using PolInSAR based approaches.

4.2.1 Validation of Height Products

Before assessing the relationship between coherence and forest structure, it is essential to evaluate the accuracy of the height layers derived from spaceborn sources. In this study, both the CHM and DTM were validated against ALS data for the regions of Kotka and Joensuu, in Finland. Figures 29 and 30 show the comparison between ALS derived heights and spaceborne CHM and DTM for Kotka and Joensuu respectively.

Figure 29: Comparison between spaceborne and ALS derived height products over Kotka. (a) CHM vs. ALS canopy height. (b) DTM vs. ALS ground elevation.

In Kotka, the CHM exhibits a clear overestimation of canopy height for taller forest, particularly above 25m. This is visible in the deviation from the 1:1 reference line and the increasing dispersion at higher values. The DTM, in contrast, shows very good agreement with ALS, with minimal bias and tight clustering around the diagonal. This is confirmed by the correlation values, as seen in table 5.

Figure 30: Comparison between spaceborne and ALS derived height products over Joensuu. (a) CHM vs. ALS canopy height. (b) DTM vs. ALS ground elevation.

In Joensuu, the patterns is similar but more pronounced. The CHM not only overestimates canopy height but also shows a negative correlation with ALS measurements, likely due to data mismatch or sensor limitations. Meanwhile, the DTM displays perfect correlation with ALS, confirming its reliability for use in elevation correction and phase normalization.

This findings confirm that while the spaceborne DTM can be used with high confidence, the CHM requires caution, especially for tall forest stands.

Table 5: Correlation Between CHM and DTM with ALS.

Region	CHM-ALS correlation	DTM-ALS correlation
Kotka	$r=0.888$	$r=0.998$
Joensuu	$r=-0.651$	$r=1$

Consequently, throughout this thesis, ALS derived canopy height will be used as the reference layer.

4.2.2 Coherence-Height Relationship in Single Baseline Observations

According to PolInSAR theory and the RVoG model, interferometric coherence is expected to decrease with increasing forest height due to volume decorrelation. To assess whether this relationship can be observed in practice using Sentinel-1 dataset, we analyzed the

coherence-height correlation over the sites of Kotka and Joensuu using single baseline interferometric pairs and ALS derived canopy height as reference.

Table 6: Correlation Between CHM and DTM with ALS.

Region-Date	HV Channel	VV Channel
Kotka - 17 to 29 Jun, 2020	$r=-0.134$	$r=-0.179$
Joensuu - 7 to 19 Sept, 2024	$r=-0.127$	$r=-0.142$

In Kotka, the pair from 17-29 June 2020 was selected to match the available airborne LiDAR campaign. Figure 31 show scatter plot of coherence vs. ALS canopy height for HV and VV polarizations respectively. While the relationship is not strongly pronounced, a negative correlation is visible in both channels.

Figure 31: Scatter plots of Sentinel-1 coherence vs. CHM derived from ALS data in Kotka for the acquisition pair 17-29 of June, 2020. (a) Coherence in HV polarization. (b) Coherence in VV polarization.

The values observed in Table 6, indicate that although coherence decreases slightly with increasing forest height, the effect is weak when using a single interferometric pair, likely due to temporal decorrelation and residual noise.

A similar analysis was performed in Joensuu using the Sentinel-1 pair from 7-19 September 2024, matched to the 2024 ALS dataset. The results in the Figure 32 show slightly stronger negative correlations.

Figure 32: Scatter plots of Sentinel-1 coherence vs. CHM derived from ALS data in Joensuu for the acquisition pair 7-19 of September, 2024. (a) Coherence in HV polarization. (b) Coherence in VV polarization,

While the absolute values in Table 6 remains low, the expected inverse relationship between coherence and forest height is consistent across both regions and both polarizations.

To better capture the general trend of coherence as a function of forest height, the data were also grouped into 5m canopy height intervals, and the mean coherence was computed within each bin. The resulting profiles are shown in Figure 33, for both Kotka and Joensuu, and for both Channels.

Figure 33: Mean interferometric coherence values per canopy height bin. Red lines correspond to VV polarization and blue lines to VH polarization. (a) Kotka. (b) Joensuu.

In both regions, clear decreasing trend is observed, mean coherence systematically decreases as canopy height increases, consistent with expectations from volume decorrela-

tion models. The effect is more pronounced in the VV channel, which consistently shows higher coherence values across all height ranges. The flattening of the curves above 20m suggest that coherence becomes less sensitive to additional height increases in dense forest canopies, potentially due to saturation or signal attenuation. These profiles help mitigate the effects of local variability and confirm the structural dependence of Sentinel-1 coherence on forest height at regional scale.

Overall, these results suggest that, although single baseline coherence from Sentinel-1 can reflect some structural sensitivity, the effect is subtle and easily masked by noise, temporal decorrelation or geometric mismatches.

4.2.3 Temporal Coherence Statistics

Temporal coherence stability is a key indicator of structural consistency in forested areas. In this section, we analyze the temporal behavior of Sentinel-1 interferometric coherence over the Kotka test site by evaluating three complementary aspects, temporal variability, linear trends and the dominant temporal modes extracted via Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

All analyses are based on a time series of eight Sentinel-1 acquisitions from May to August 2020, aligned with ALS derived canopy height.

4.2.3.1 Temporal Variability and Height Dependency

To evaluate the stability of coherence over time, the standard deviation of coherence was computed for each pixel across eight Sentinel-1 acquisitions in the Kotka region. This metric quantifies how much coherence fluctuates for a given location and is used to assess the structural stability of the canopy.

The standard deviation values were grouped into 5 m canopy height bins using ALS derived heights. Results are presented in Figures 34 and 35.

Figure 34: Standard deviation of interferometric coherence as a function of canopy height in Kotka, grouped in 5 m bins, HV polarization.

In both HV and VV channels, coherence variability is higher for short vegetation (≤ 10 m) and decreases progressively as canopy height increases. The effect is more pronounced in the HV channel, with variability dropping significantly between 15-30 m.

Figure 35: Standard deviation of interferometric coherence as a function of canopy height in Kotka, grouped in 5 m bins, VV polarization.

This suggest that taller and denser forests exhibit more stable temporal coherence, likely due to their structural maturity and lower sensitivity to environmental changes. This property is particularly useful for identifying stable vegetated targets in SAR time series analysis.

4.2.3.2 Temporal Trend Analysis

Beyond variability, the temporal trend of coherence was examined by fitting a linear regression model at each pixel,

$$\gamma(t) = a \cdot t + b, \quad (37)$$

where a is the slope indicating whether coherence increases or decreases over time. The slope values were then plotted against ALS derived canopy height to explore structural dependencies.

As shown in Figure 36, a slight positive trend in coherence is observed with increasing height, especially in the VV channel, where the correlation reaches $r = 0.2$. In the HV channel, the correlation is weaker, $r = 0.08$ but still positive.

Figure 36: Temporal slope of coherence, from linear regression, as a function of canopy height in Kotka. (a) HV polarization. (b) VV polarization.

This implies that coherence tends to increase over time in taller canopies, possibly due to seasonal stabilization effects, e.g., reduced soil moisture variability in summer, or improved volume scattering consistency in mature forest. Although the trend is not strong, its consistency across channels supports the hypothesis that forest structure influences temporal coherence dynamics.

4.2.3.3 Temporal Trend Analysis

To investigate dominant temporal patterns in the coherence series, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied separately to HV and VV time series for each pixel.

Figures 37 and 38 show the percentage of variance explained by the first three principal components (PCs).

Figure 37: Percentage of variance explained by the first three principal components in HV polarization over the Kotka time series.

Figure 38: Percentage of variance explained by the first three principal components in VV polarization over the Kotka time series.

As seen, PC1 accounts for the majority of the variability in VH channel, 23%, and 31% in VV channel. This confirms that coherence time series are dominated by a single trend, likely linked to average coherence level or overall structural stability.

To assess whether these components are influenced by forest height, the scores of PC1-PC3 were plotted against ALS canopy height in Figures 39 and 40.

Figure 39: Scatter plots of PCA scores (PC1-PC3) vs. canopy height for HV polarization.

A moderate negative correlation is observed between PC1 and height, for the HV channel, $r = -0.22$ and for the VV channel, $r = -0.27$,

Figure 40: Scatter plots of PCA scores (PC1-PC3) vs. canopy height for VV polarization.

This means that the main temporal mode of coherence decreases with increasing canopy height, further confirming that forest structure has a measurable influence on coherence evolution.

Together with the previous analyses, PCA reveals that coherence time series are not

random, they carry structural information that can be exploited in filtering and modeling processes.

4.2.4 Physically-Based Filtering Using RVoG Constraints

The final stage in the structural validation pipeline involves applying a set of physically motivated filters to isolate the subset of observations that are consistent with theoretical expectations from the RVoG model. As explained in chapter 2.4, this model establishes a relationship between coherence magnitude, forest height and acquisition geometry. However, in real-world datasets, coherence is affected by noise, temporal decorrelation and geometric distortions that must be mitigated to ensure robust model fitting.

This section details a three step filtering framework that integrates temporal statistics, spatial structure and physical modeling to retain only high quality, structural consistent coherence-height samples.

4.2.4.1 Temporal Stability Filter

The first step is based on the assumption that physically meaningful pixels should exhibit stable coherence over time. In forested areas, large temporal fluctuations in coherence are often linked to acquisition artifacts, weather conditions or land cover changes. To quantify this, we computed the standard deviation of coherence across eight Sentinel-1 acquisitions for each pixel, separately for HV and VV channels.

Pixels with a temporal standard deviation lower than 0.02 were removed from further analysis. These extremely stable responses are not necessarily reliable, often associated with non-vegetated surfaces, shadows or system noise, where coherence is consistently low or dominated by speckle.

Figure 41: Temporal standard deviation of coherence in Kotka for HV polarization.

Figure 42: Temporal standard deviation of coherence in Kotka for VV polarization.

Figures 41 and 42 illustrate the spatial distribution of the valid pixels. This filter retained 99.98% of HV pixels and 99.99% of VV pixels, meaning its impact is minor but useful for removing obviously invalid cases at the margins of the dataset.

4.2.4.2 Spatial Gradient Filter

The second filter addresses the issue of mixed pixels and forest edges, which violate the assumptions of homogeneity underlying the RVoG model. Sudden transitions in canopy height, such as stand borders, clearcuts or mixed land cover, can cause strong spatial gradients in the CHM, leading to unreliable coherence measurements that do not reflect a pure volume-ground interaction.

To detect these transitions, we computed the magnitude of the spatial gradient of the CHM for each pixel. A binary mask was then generated by thresholding the gradient magnitude using the 95th percentile, discarding the top 5% most abrupt transitions in forest structure.

Figure 43: Spatial gradient filter over Kotka for HV channel.

Figure 44: Spatial gradient filter over Kotka for VV channel.

This filter was particularly effective at removing high slope areas at forest edges and along road boundaries. Figures 43 and 44 show the CHM gradient map and the resulting filtered mask. The effect is spatially localized but important for ensuring structural homogeneity in the retained pixels.

4.2.4.3 Model-Based RVoG Filtering

The final and most selective filter directly leverages the analytical expression of the RVoG model. Using the ALS derived canopy height and the known vertical wavenumber kz for each pixel, we computed the expected coherence based on a reference RVoG configuration with fixed parameters, $M = 1.35$ and $\sigma = 0.1$.

This theoretical coherence curve was compared to the observed coherence from the Sentinel-1 acquisitions. Pixels where $|\gamma_{obs} - \gamma_{mod}| > 0.1$ were discarded.

Figure 45: RVoG filtering over Kotka region. (a) HV channel. (b) VV channel.

This physically based filtering step is highly selective, only 0.04% of HV samples and 0.1% of VV samples were retained. Nevertheless, as illustrated in Figure 45, the remaining points align closely with the expected coherence-height relationship described by the RVoG model, forming a clean and interpretable dataset ideal for model inversion.

As a final analysis, the retained observations after all filtering steps were normalized by their corresponding HoA to produce a dimensionless height parameter h/HoA . This normalization allows for generalization of the RVoG model across acquisitions with varying kz values.

Figure 46: Observed coherence as a function of normalized height for both polarizations. The dashed curves represent the fitted RVoG model.

The coherence values were binned by normalized height and averaged to obtain a smoothed profile of the coherence-height relationship. Figure 46 shows the result, along with an extended RVoG fit including a scaling parameter A . The fitted curves capture the general decreasing trend of coherence with normalized height, showing a reasonable agreement with the binned data. This supports the theoretical expectations of the RVoG model under average conditions, although individual sample variability remains high due to structural and acquisition related factors.

Figure 47: Distribution of normalized height values computed from airborne LiDAR and interferometric ambiguity height.

Additionally, Figure 47 presents the histogram of h/HoA values in the filtered dataset, illustrating that most samples correspond to low normalized heights, which aligns with the relatively short forest stands in the Kotka region.

5 Conclusions

This thesis has demonstrated the feasibility of retrieving forest structural parameters, particularly canopy height, from L-band PolInSAR data using physical scattering models. The RVoG and RMoG models were successfully adapted and fitted to airborne datasets from Estonia and Finland, showing high correlation between modeled coherence and LiDAR-derived height. In contrast, Sentinel-1 C-band time-series coherence data, while rich in temporal information, did not correlate strongly with canopy height, motivating an in-depth analysis of its temporal and seasonal patterns.

The theoretical foundation was progressively introduced from electromagnetic wave modeling and polarimetric SAR representations to advanced concepts of interferometric and polarimetric coherence. Particular emphasis was placed on the interpretation of coherence as a measurable indicator of vertical forest structure enabling the inversion of canopy height.

In the first part of the analysis, the RVoG model was successfully fitted to airborne LiDAR reference heights over boreal forest regions in Estonia and Finland using single baseline and single pass acquisitions. The relationship between interferometric coherence and normalized canopy height was clearly observed and consistent across different forest types. Subsequently, the RMoG model was applied as an extension to account for temporal decorrelation, resulting in better fits under longer temporal baselines and more complex scenes. These findings demonstrate reliability of physically based models in controlled conditions and validate their use in forest parameter inversion.

However, when applying the same framework to the Sentinel-1 repeat pass dataset, which introduces a 12 day temporal baseline, the behavior diverged significantly. The correlation between interferometric coherence and canopy height was weak and inconsistent, for both polarizations, HV and VV. This loss of relationship is attributed to strong temporal decorrelation effects, which can not be fully explained by the volume scattering models alone.

In response, an exhaustive exploratory analysis was conducted on the Sentinel-1 data to assess whether coherence exhibited any patterns or dependencies that could be modeled. The dataset was analyzed across different dimensions, including time, incident angle and vertical wavenumber, despite this effort, the correlation matrices showed that the relationships between coherence and key structural or geometric variables remained low, particularly during high vegetation periods as in summer.

This findings underscore the limitations of applying conventional RVoG based inversion to Sentinel-1 temporal baselines without further correction or compensation mechanisms. They also highlight the necessity of accounting for decorrelation sources explicitly when working with temporal baselines in boreal forest environments.

Among the key observations, physically based models showed good agreement with airborne datasets, especially in single pass conditions. Temporal decorrelation in Sentinel-1 data led to significant loss of structural information, which limited the reliability of inversion. Seasonal analysis and multitemporal coherence trends suggest that external factors may play a stronger role in decorrelation than previously assumed. No clear or modelable

dependence on height was recovered from Sentinel-1 under 12 day baselines, emphasizing the need for further work in this direction.

5.1 Future Work

The limitations and findings identified throughout this thesis open up several promising directions for future research and methodological improvements.

Incorporation of Machine Learning approaches, given the weak correlation between coherence and canopy height in Sentinel-1 data, incorporate these techniques may help detect hidden patterns or nonlinear relationships not captured by traditional physical models. Enhanced modeling of temporal decorrelation, as the RMoG model accounts for general decorrelation effects, but additional efforts are needed to characterize specific mechanisms such as wind induced motion, seasonal moisture changes or phenological variability, extending the physical models to explicitly include these factors to training data could improve their predictive power in operational scenarios. Integration of multi frequency and multi baseline observations, combining L-band data with C-band or P-band acquisitions could help with the volume and temporal effects due to their differing penetration depths and decorrelation behaviors. One major limitation is the dependency on LiDAR derived canopy heights for calibrating the model's parameters, developing unsupervised or semi-supervised inversion methods using PolInSAR observables alone could enable large scale forest height estimation without external reference datasets. While this work focused on boreal forest in Estonia, Finland, Sweden and Norway, extending the methodology to tropical or temperate forest would test its generalization and robustness. Differences in structure, moisture regime and temporal dynamics may lead to alternative model behaviors or require new parameterizations

These future directions aim to overcome current model limitations, exploit the full potential of polarimetric and interferometric observables and contribute toward scalable and accurate forest monitoring solutions based on SAR technologies.

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Appendices

Geometry and Equations of InSAR

This Annex presents the basic geometry of a Synthetic Aperture Radar Interferometer (InSAR) and explains how this configuration enables the estimation of terrain topography from the interferometric phase difference. Figure ?? shows the basic schematic of an InSAR system, where two antennas or two positions of the same SAR sensor (1 and 2) observe the same point on the ground with a spatial separation known as the interferometric baseline B [8, 42].

Generic Geometry of a SAR Interferometer.

As shown, some of the key elements in InSAR geometry include the observation platform at a height, H , which represents the altitude of the satellite or airborne platform relative to a reference datum taken as zero elevation. The incidence angle θ , formed between the radar line of sight and the vertical at the surface point. The distances R_1 and R_2 , from each radar position to the target on the ground, are essential, as SAR images capture information in the form of phase, and the difference in path length between these distances is critical to the measurement. Finally, the phase difference $\delta\theta$, which represents the angular variation in the observation direction due to the antenna separation, is used to infer the height h of the point on the ground.

If the acquisition geometry is known, i.e, the sensor positions, incidence angle and baseline, it is possible to calculate the terrain topography as a function of the interferometric phase difference.

First, equations (38) and (39) are presented, which correspond to the received radar signal model and help to understand how the total phase of the SAR signal is formed as a function of the target distance. We begin with the expression,

$$E^r(t) = A\rho e^{(j\omega t - \phi_T)}, \quad (38)$$

this is a complex representation of the radar signal received after being reflected from a target, and it is a standard way of modeling electromagnetic waves in radar systems [9]. Here, $E^r(t)$ denotes the amplitude of the received signal as a function of time, A , is a calibration constant, ρ , is the reflection (backscatter) coefficient of the ground target, w , is the angular frequency of the radar ($w = 2\pi f$) and ϕ_T is the total phase of the received signal. This equation shows that the phase information resides in the exponent, which is precisely what is measured and compared between two SAR acquisitions in InSAR. On the other hand,

$$\phi_T = 2\beta R = 2 \cdot \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \cdot R = \frac{4\pi R}{\lambda}, \quad (39)$$

is the expression of the total propagation phase of a radar wave as a function of the distance R , traveled to the target and back [8]. These equations are important because they show that phase is not an abstract phenomenon, but is directly related to the physical distance to the target. If the terrain height changes, the value of R changes accordingly and therefore so does ϕ_T . This forms the basis for reconstructing elevation models from differential phase measurements.

Defining the distances,

$$R_1 = R_2 \cos(\delta\theta) + B \sin(\theta) \quad (40)$$

$$R_1 = R_2 + B \sin(\theta), \quad (41)$$

and the path difference as,

$$\Delta R = R_1 - R_2 = B \sin(\theta) \quad (42)$$

we can now present the mathematical equations that allow the terrain height h to be calculated from the phase difference $\Delta\phi$. Equation (43) defines the interferometric phase difference under ideal condition [33] as,

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{4\pi B \sin \theta}{\lambda}, \quad (43)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the SAR signal. This equation captures the fundamental component that allows the SAR signal to be related to terrain elevation. However, this is a simplified model, for accurate topographic estimations, the actual system geometry and orbital parameters must be taken into account.

To quantify the system's sensitivity to changes in topography, the equation that relates phase variation to changes in terrain height is derived [42],

$$\frac{d(\Delta\phi)}{dh} = \frac{4\pi B_{\perp}}{\lambda R_0 \sin(\theta)} = \frac{4\pi B_{\perp} \cos(\theta)}{\lambda H \sin(\theta)}. \quad (44)$$

Here, the parameter B_{\perp} is introduced, representing the perpendicular baseline, which determines how sensitive the interferometric phase is to changes in terrain height. The greater the value of B_{\perp} , the larger the phase variation for the same change in h . This leads to the definition of the interferometric sensitivity factor α_{IF} as,

$$\alpha_{IF} = \frac{dh}{d(\Delta\phi)}, \quad (45)$$

and therefore, the topography can be expressed as a function of the interferometric phase as,

$$h(x, y) = \alpha_{IF} \cdot \Delta\phi(x, y) + cte. \quad (46)$$

This relationship forms the basis of algorithms used for generating Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) from InSAR data.

Figure ?? presents a more general and realistic scenario, in which the baseline is not perfectly perpendicular but is inclined at an angle α with respect to the vertical axis.

Realistic Geometry of a SAR Interferometer with Inclined Baseline.

In this case, the effective observation angle changes and the perpendicular component of the baseline is adjusted as,

$$B_{\perp} = B \cos(\alpha), \quad (47)$$

also affecting the interferometric sensitivity, which is expressed as,

$$\frac{d(\Delta\phi)}{dh} = \frac{4\pi B_{\perp} \cos(\theta - \alpha)}{\lambda H \sin(\theta)}. \quad (48)$$

The interpretation is that the inclination of the baseline reduces the system's effective vertical sensitivity. Therefore, in real operational configurations [8, 42], it is essential to accurately know the system's geometry and orientation in order to obtain reliable height estimates.

Interrelation Between Scattering Coefficients, Matrices and Coherence

All radar-based forest structure estimation models developed in this thesis are ultimately derived from the fundamental radar measurement, the complex scattering coefficients S_{pq} , which describe the amplitude and phase of the backscattered electromagnetic signal for each transmit-receive polarization pair [9].

These coefficients are grouped into the scattering matrix S , introduced in (??), which serves as the starting point for all polarimetric analysis [33]. Each component $S_{pq} = |S_{pq}|e^{j\phi_{pq}}$ represents a coherent radar measurement from the observed resolution cell.

From the matrix S , two vector representations are constructed, the lexicographic vector $s = [S_{HH}, S_{HV}, S_{VV}]^T$ and the Pauli vector $k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[S_{HH} + S_{VV}, S_{HH} - S_{VV}, 2S_{HV}]^T$. These vectors are used to derive the second order statistics, the Covariance matrix, $C = \langle s \cdot s^H \rangle$ and the Coherency matrix, $T = \langle k \cdot k^H \rangle$.

These matrices capture the spatial and polarimetric structure of the scene and are the basis for polarimetric decompositions [33] and coherence modeling. In interferometric applications, the same matrix elements $S_{pq}^{(1)}$ and $S_{pq}^{(2)}$ are acquired from two slightly different positions. The interferometric coherence is then computed from these complex measurements,

$$\gamma = \frac{\langle S_{pq}^{(1)} \cdot S_{pq}^{(2)*} \rangle}{\sqrt{\langle |S_{pq}^{(1)}|^2 \rangle \cdot \langle |S_{pq}^{(2)}|^2 \rangle}}. \quad (49)$$

In PolInSAR, these individual channel coherences are generalized by projecting the full scattering vectors into arbitrary polarization directions \vec{w} , and evaluating the resulting complex coherence [25],

$$\gamma(\vec{w}) = \frac{\vec{w}^t \cdot T_{12} \cdot \vec{w}}{\sqrt{(\vec{w}^t \cdot T_{11} \cdot \vec{w}) \cdot (\vec{w}^t \cdot T_{22} \cdot \vec{w})}}. \quad (50)$$

This formulation reveals how the physical models such as RVoG and RMoG rely on coherence values that originate directly from the scattering coefficients through the above chain

$$S_{pq} \Rightarrow S \Rightarrow s, k \Rightarrow C, T \Rightarrow \gamma \quad (51)$$

Hence, all model inputs and observed variables are traceable to the original radar measurements S_{pq} , making these coefficients the fundamental link between SAR observables and forest structure modeling [33].

Correlation Between Interferometric Variables

This annex complements Chapter 3 by presenting graphical and tabulated results of the correlation analysis between forest height, coherence and interferometric phase. The analysis was conducted separately by region, Järvelja and Soomaa, as well as by forest type, pine, spruce and deciduous. The results shown here provide a more detailed visualization of data distribution, correlation direction and statistical robustness of the observed trends, reinforcing the conclusions presented in the results section of the thesis.

Correlation Coefficients Between Height and Interferometric Coherence by Region.

Region	Coherence vs. Height
Järvelja	$r=-0.822$
Soomaa	$r=-0.441$

Correlation Coefficients Between Height and Interferometric Phase by Region.

Region	Coherence vs. Phase
Järvelja	$r=-0.621$
Soomaa	$r=-0.711$

Correlations by Forest Type.

Forest Type	Coherence vs. Height	Phase vs. Height
Pine	$r=-0.6$	$r=-0.86$
Spruce	$r=-0.73$	$r=-0.76$
Deciduous	$r=-0.59$	$r=-0.59$

Representation of the relationship between Interferometric Coherence and Forest Height in the overall dataset.

Representation of the relationship between Interferometric Phase and Forest Height in the overall dataset.

Relationship between Interferometric Coherence and Height in each region.

Relationship between Interferometric Phase and Height in each region.

Relationship between Interferometric Coherence and Height by forest type in the overall dataset.

Relationship between Interferometric Phase and Height by forest type in the overall dataset.

Relationship between Interferometric Coherence and Height by forest type in Järvselja region.

Relationship between Interferometric Coherence and Height by forest type in Soomaa region.

Relationship between Interferometric Phase and Height by forest type in Järvelja region.

Relationship between Interferometric Phase and Height by forest type in Soomaa region.

The results presented in this Annex provide a solid statistical basis for supporting the use of the interferometric coherence and phase as structural variables in forest height estimation. The observed relationships reinforce the theoretical framework and validate the application of the RVoG and RMoG models in this work. It is observed that the correlation is stronger in homogeneous forests and in areas with lower structural variability, whereas in more dynamic environments such as Soomaa, the data dispersion suggest the need to consider more advanced models that incorporate canopy motion effects.

Matlab codes

Function to read the Dataset

```

1 function DataAll = ReadData(rootFolder, siteName)
2 % Look for all the .mat in the folders
3 allFiles = dir(fullfile(rootFolder, '**', '*.mat'));
4 DataAll = []; % Inicialization
5 for i = 1:length(allFiles)
6     try
7         filepath = fullfile(allFiles(i).folder, allFiles(i).name);
8         load(filepath); % load the variables: I, Lidar, dataInfo,
9             IncidentAngle, etc.
10        % === Coherences Estimation
11        windSize = 5;
12        covariance = cell(4,4);
13        covariance_n = cell(4,4);
14        for ii = 1:4
15            for jj = 1:4
16                covariance{ii,jj} = imfilter(squeeze(I(:,:,ii)) .* conj(
17                    squeeze(I(:,:,jj))), ...
18                    fspecial('average', windSize), 'replicate');
19            end
20        end
21        for ii = 1:4
22            for jj = 1:4
23                denom = sqrt(imfilter(abs(squeeze(I(:,:,ii)).^2),
24                    fspecial('average', windSize), 'replicate') .* ...
25                    imfilter(abs(squeeze(I(:,:,jj)).^2),
26                        fspecial('average', windSize), '
27                        replicate'));
28                covariance_n{ii,jj} = covariance{ii,jj} ./ denom;
29            end
30        end
31        coherenceHV = covariance_n{1,3};
32        coherenceVV = covariance_n{2,4};
33        % === SAR Parameters
34        bn = str2double(dataInfo("Perp Baseline")); % Bperp
35        lambda = 0.05546; % Wavelength C-band (m)
36        H = 693000; % Height of the satellite in meters
37        m = 2;
38        HoA = (lambda * H .* sind(IncidentAngle)) ./ (bn * cosd(
39            IncidentAngle) * m);
40        kz = (2 * pi) ./ HoA;
41        % === Lidar
42        LidarH = getfield(Lidar, 'Lidar RH98');
43        Ground = getfield(Lidar, 'Lidar ground elevation');
44        mask = ~isnan(LidarH) & LidarH > 0;
45        % === Metadata
46        modelledCoh = str2double(dataInfo("Modelled Coherence"));
47        hoa_global = str2double(dataInfo("Height of Ambiguity"));
48        rh98_global = dataInfo("Tree Height (RH98)");
49        range_center = dataInfo("Range distance (meter)");
50        inc_center = dataInfo("Incident Angle (degree)");
51        lat_center = dataInfo("Latitude");

```

```

46 lon_center = dataInfo("Longitude");
47 masterDate = datetime(dataInfo('SAR master date'), 'InputFormat
    ', 'ddMMMyyyy');
48 slaveDate = datetime(dataInfo('SAR slave date'), 'InputFormat
    ', 'ddMMMyyyy');
49 % === Build a table for this file
50 T = table;
51 T.CoherenceHV = abs(coherenceHV(mask));
52 T.CoherenceVV = abs(coherenceVV(mask));
53 T.PhaseHV = angle(coherenceHV(mask));
54 T.PhaseVV = angle(coherenceVV(mask));
55 T.LaserH = LidarH(mask);
56 T.GroundElev = Ground(mask);
57 T.Bperp = repmat(bn, sum(mask(:)), 1);
58 T.HoA = HoA(mask);
59 T.Kz = kz(mask);
60 T.Incidence = IncidentAngle(mask);
61 T.Range = Range(mask);
62 T.Latitude = Latitude(mask);
63 T.Longitude = Longitude(mask);
64 T.TimestampMaster = repmat(masterDate, sum(mask(:)), 1);
65 T.TimestampSlave = repmat(slaveDate, sum(mask(:)), 1);
66 T.FileName = repmat({allFiles(i).name}, sum(mask(:)),
    1);
67 T.Site = repmat({siteName}, sum(mask(:)), 1);
68 % Global variables
69 T.ModelledCoh = repmat(modelledCoh, sum(mask(:)), 1);
70 T.HoA_global = repmat(hoa_global, sum(mask(:)), 1);
71 T.TreeH_global = repmat(rh98_global, sum(mask(:)), 1);
72 T.Inc_center = repmat(inc_center, sum(mask(:)), 1);
73 T.Range_center = repmat(range_center, sum(mask(:)), 1);
74 T.Lat_center = repmat(lat_center, sum(mask(:)), 1);
75 T.Lon_center = repmat(lon_center, sum(mask(:)), 1);
76 DataAll = [DataAll; T];
77 catch ME
78     warning("Processing Error %s: %s", allFiles(i).name, ME.message
    );
79     end
80 end
81 % === Save the table
82 save(['Data_' siteName '.mat'], 'DataAll');
83 end

```

Listing 1: Function to read the Dataset

RVoG function

```

1 function [Yv, Y , M] =RVoG_func(X,Par,ph);
2 % X - function arguments X(:,1)=kz, X(:,2)=treeheight
3 % Par - function parameters Par(1)=used by all models
4 % Par(2) used only by RVoG model for extinction
5 Penalty=0;
6 % Penalty function is used to restrict parameter values to feasible
   range % RVoG model
7 if Par(1)>6;
8     Penalty=1;
9 end;
10 h=X(:,1); %Tree Height
11 kz=X(:,2); %kz
12 ext=abs(Par(2)); %Extinction coefficient
13 M=abs(Par(1)).^2;
14 %Volume decorrelation
15 Yv=(exp(h.*(ext+i.*kz))-1)./((exp(h.*ext)-1).*(1+kz.*i./ext));
16 %Overall decorrelation
17 Y=exp(i*ph).*((Yv-1).*(1./(1+(1./M).*exp(h.*ext)))+1)+Penalty;
18 end

```

Listing 2: RVoG function

RMoG function

```

1 function [Yv, Y, M] = RMoG_func(X, Par, ph)
2 % RMoG_func - Random Motion over Ground Model
3 % X(:,1) = Tree height (h)
4 % X(:,2) = kz
5 % Par(1) = M (ground-to-volume ratio)[0.5-3-5]
6 % Par(2) = ext (extinction coefficient)[0.01-0.1]
7 % Par(3) = sigmaV (temporal decorrelation coefficient for volume)
8 % Par(4) = sigmaG (temporal decorrelation coefficient for ground)
9 % ph = interferometric ground phase
10 Penalty = 0;
11 % Penalty for non physical param.
12 if Par(1) > 6
13     Penalty = 1;
14 end
15 % Model variables
16 h = X(:,1); % Tree height
17 kz = X(:,2); % kz
18 ext = abs(Par(2)); % Extinction coefficient (positiv)
19 sigmaV = abs(Par(3)); % Temporal decorrelation - Volume
20 sigmaG = abs(Par(4)); % Temporal decorrelation - Ground
21 % Ground-volume relationship
22 M = abs(Par(1)).^2;
23 % Volumetric decorrelation (as RVoG)
24 Yv = (exp(h .* (ext + 1i .* kz)) - 1) ./ ((exp(h .* ext) - 1) .* (1 + 1i
25     * kz ./ ext));
26 % Temporal decorrelation for the volume
27 Yv = Yv .* exp(-sigmaV);
28 % Ground term with temporal decorrelation
29 GroundTerm = (1 ./ (1 + (1 ./ M) .* exp(h .* ext))) .* exp(-sigmaG);
30 % Total Coherence (RMoG)
31 Y = exp(1i * ph) .* ((Yv - 1) .* GroundTerm + 1) + Penalty;
end

```

Listing 3: RMoG function

Full Analysis of Correlations Between Interferometric Coherence and Tree Height using Sentinel-1 Dataset

This annex presents a detailed analysis of the relationship between Sentinel-1 interferometric coherence and tree height derived from ICESat-2, focused on data acquired over Norway, Sweden and Finland. The main objective is to assess whether a significant correlation exists between forest height and interferometric coherence under different acquisition conditions, such as seasonal variations, incidence angles, specific acquisition dates and changes in the Kz parameter. To this end, grouped visualizations or correlation analyses are employed to interpret the data.

In theory, coherence is expected to decrease with increasing vegetation height due to greater volume decorrelation. However, the results show that this correlation is weak or inconsistent across the dataset. The following sections present various visual and quantitative analyses that allow this complexity to be explored.

Only a selected subset of these results is included in the main text, the remaining visualizations are provided here for completeness and transparency.

Norway and Sweden

Coherence vs canopy height and complex plane scatterplot for both channels.

Coherence vs. canopy height with k-means clustering (HV) channel.

Exploring by Dates

May 20, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 31, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 17, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

April 21, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

May 27, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 24, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 24-Jun-2024

June 24, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 25-Jul-2024

July 25, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

August 23, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 28, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Exploring by Season

Coherence vs Tree Height - Autumn

Coherence distribution in autumn.

Coherence vs Tree Height - Spring

Coherence distribution in spring.

Coherence distribution in summer.

Seasonal distribution of coherence grouped by spring, summer and autumn.

Exploring by Height

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (0–3m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (3–6m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (6–9m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (9–12m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (12–15m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (15–18m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (21–24m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (24–27m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (27–30m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (30–33m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (33–36m) in Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (36–39m) in Sweden and Norway.

Exploring by Angle of Incidence

Coherence vs. height with $30^\circ < \theta^\circ < 34^\circ$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $34^\circ < \theta^\circ < 38^\circ$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $38^\circ < \theta^\circ < 42^\circ$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $42^\circ < \theta^\circ < 46^\circ$ for Sweden and Norway.

Exploring by kz

Coherence vs. height with $-0.1 < Kz < -0.05$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $-0.05 < Kz < 0$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $0 < Kz < 0.05$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $0.05 < Kz < 0.1$ for Sweden and Norway.

Coherence vs. height with $0.1 < Kz < 0.15$ for Sweden and Norway.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation matrix between coherence and all variables.

Correlation matrix between coherence and height in autumn.

Correlation matrix between coherence and height in spring.

Correlation matrix between coherence and height in summer.

Finland

Coherence vs canopy height and complex plane scatterplot for both channels.

Coherence vs. canopy height with k-means clustering (HV) channel.

Exploring by Dates

July 29, 2019: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 23, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 24-Jun-2021

June 24, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 29, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 30, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

August 29, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 23, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 28, 2021: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 27-Apr-2022

April 27, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 21-May-2022

May 21, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 26, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 19, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 20, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 25, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 25-Aug-2022

August 25, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 28-Aug-2022

August 28, 2022: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

April 23, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

April 24, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

May 31, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 2, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 21, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 29, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 1, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 24, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 25, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 29, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 23-Aug-2023

August 23, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 29-Aug-2023

August 29, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

August 30, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 23, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 24-Sep-2023

September 24, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 28-Sep-2023

September 28, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 30-Sep-2023

September 30, 2023: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

April 27, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 26, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

June 27, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 2, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 21-Jul-2024

July 21, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

July 26, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 21-Aug-2024

August 21, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Coherence vs Tree Height - 25-Aug-2024

August 25, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

August 26, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

August 31, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 24, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 19, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

September 30, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

October 30, 2024: Coherence vs. canopy height (HV and VV) and complex plane.

Exploring by Season

Coherence vs Tree Height - Spring

Seasonal distribution of coherence in spring.

Coherence vs Tree Height - Summer

Seasonal distribution of coherence in summer.

Seasonal distribution of coherence in autumn.

Seasonal distribution of coherence grouped by spring, summer and autumn.

Exploring by Height

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (0–3m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (3–6m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (6-9m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (9-12m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (15–18m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (18–21m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (27–30m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (30–33m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (33–36m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (36–39m) in Finland.

Coherence vs. height in 3m height bins (39-42m) in Finland.

Exploring by Angle of Incidence

Coherence vs. height with $30^\circ < \theta^\circ < 34^\circ$ for Finland.

Coherence vs. height with $34^\circ < \theta^\circ < 38^\circ$ for Finland.

Coherence vs. height with $38^\circ < \theta^\circ < 42^\circ$ for Finland.

Coherence vs. height with $42^\circ < \theta^\circ < 48^\circ$ for Finland.

Exploring by kz

Coherence vs. height with $-0.05 < Kz < 0$ for Finland.

Coherence vs. height with $0 < Kz < 0.05$ for Finland.

Coherence vs. height with $0.05 < Kz < 0.1$ for Finland.

Correlation Matrix

Correlation matrix between coherence and all variables.

Correlation matrix between coherence and height in spring.

Correlation matrix between coherence and height in summer.

Correlation matrix between coherence and height in autumn.